

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students

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ABSTRACT

The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students

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This study examines the impact of comfort room cleanliness on the academic engagement of senior high school students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study collected data from 307 senior high school students across various academic strands through a researcher-made survey questionnaire. The results indicate that students predominantly perceive the comfort rooms as dirty, citing poor maintenance, lack of hygiene products, and foul odors as key issues. Although students believe that clean restrooms contribute to their comfort, focus, and overall well-being, no direct relationship was found between comfort room cleanliness and overall academic engagement. However, student satisfaction, concentration, and health were positively associated with cleanliness, suggesting that clean comfort rooms indirectly support a positive learning environment. The study recommends establishing school policies for regular cleaning, running hygiene awareness campaigns, providing sanitation supplies, and involving students in clean-up activities. For future research, it is suggested to explore how academic participation might influence these efforts and to employ qualitative methods for a deeper understanding of these factors.

Key Concepts: Comfort room cleanliness, academic engagement, student satisfaction, focus and concentration, sanitation supplies and hygiene products, school environment and infrastructure, health and well-being of students, descriptive-correlational research design, student perceptions of cleanliness, indirect impact of cleanliness on academic performance, school policies and hygiene maintenance, learning atmosphere, educational facilities management, vandalism and restroom conditions, student involvement in cleanliness initiatives, educational outcomes and learning environment, hygiene awareness campaigns, restroom maintenance and student engagement, academic focus and well-being, impact of cleanliness on school experience, academic performance.

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Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Content	Page no.
Title Page	I
Approval Sheet	II
Abstract	III
Acknowledgments	IV
Table of Content	V
List of Tables and Figures	VI

Chapter 1: THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction	1 - 3
Theoretical Framework	3 - 4
Conceptual Framework	4 - 5
Statement of the Problem	5 - 6
Hypothesis	6
Significance of the Study	6 - 8
Scope and Delimitations	8
Definition of Terms	8 - 9

Chapter 2: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

The Importance of Comfort Room Cleanliness in Educational	11 - 17
The Role of Cleanliness in Student's Academic	

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Engagement and Well-being 17 - 24

Synthesis 24 - 26

Chapter 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design 27 - 28

Population and Sampling Technique 28

Respondents of the Study 28 - 29

Instrumentation 29 - 30

Validation and Test of Reliability of Instrument 30

Data Gathering Procedure 30 - 31

Statistical Treatment of Data 31 - 33

Ethical Consideration 33

Chapter 4: PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Problem Number 1: What is the Student's Perceived level on the cleanliness of the comfort rooms? 34 - 38

Problem Number 2: How does the perceived cleanliness correlate with the following aspects of student academic engagement? 38 - 51

Problem Number 3: Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of comfort room cleanliness and overall student academic engagement? 52 - 54

Chapter 5: SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings 55 - 56

Conclusion 57

Recommendation 58 - 59

General Academic Strand

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1

Mean Responses of Student's Perceived Level of Cleanliness of Comfort Rooms (PLC).

Table 2

Table 2.1 *Mean Responses on Student Satisfaction and Comfort (ISC)*

Table 2.2 *Mean Responses on Student Focus and Concentration (IFC)*

Table 2.3 *Mean Responses on Student Health and Well-Being (IHW)*

Table 3

Significant Relationship of Comfort Room Cleanliness and Overall Academic Engagement using Pearson r

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Chapter I

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

This chapter introduces the problem and its background, it includes the hypothesis, theoretical and conceptual framework, significance of the study, scope and delimitations, definition of terms, and the hypothesis.

Introduction

The cleanliness and maintenance of school restrooms are important for the student's health, comfort, and overall academic engagement. Globally, one in three schools lacks basic sanitation facilities, leaving students to face challenges that directly affect their well-being and academic success. Research by Unilever (2021) states that poor comfort room conditions often discourage students from using them, leading to discomfort, distraction, and even absenteeism.

In Southeast Asia, the issue is particularly more common, with over 30% of schools lacking proper facilities (Eco-Business, 2018). Problems like water shortages, lack of privacy, and inadequate maintenance force students to avoid restrooms, negatively impacting their focus and performance. For girls, the situation is even worse. During menstruation, many skip schools due to the lack of proper hygiene facilities, disrupting their education and limiting future opportunities

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

In the Philippines, many public schools experience similar challenges. According to the Department of Education (DepEd), a significant number of school's lack access to clean water and functioning toilets, with Metro Manila being a prime example. Reports from Inquirer.net (2016) and GMA News (2014) highlight how non-functional and unsanitary comfort rooms cause discomfort and affect student's ability to concentrate in class resulting on poor academic engagement.

Within the campus, the lack of water on the upper floors has led to unflushed toilets, spreading unpleasant odors of human waste, such as urine and feces, into hallways and nearby classrooms. These conditions create an uncomfortable and unsanitary environment that disrupts students' ability to focus and negatively impacts their well-being and overall learning experience and academic engagement.

Research further supports these observations. Sangalang et al. (2022) emphasize that unflushed waste, bad smells, and the absence of essential cleaning materials such as soap or sanitizers lead to dirty conditions and health risks. Poor maintenance contributes to stress, distraction, and absenteeism. Neglected restrooms also lower morale, as littering and vandalism exacerbate the problem, making the school atmosphere less conducive to learning (Kleoapple, 2019)

On the other hand, clean and well-maintained restrooms significantly improve student satisfaction, health, and focus. Palar et al. (2022) highlight that better restroom management enhances hygiene and fosters a more positive school environment. Clean

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

restrooms reduce illnesses, boost confidence, and create a setting where students can concentrate on their studies without distractions.

While many studies have explored the general effects of cleanliness in schools. There remains in gap in understanding how the cleanliness of comfort rooms affects student academic engagement in senior high school students in the campus. This study addresses this gap by examining how factors such as satisfaction and comfort, focus and concentration, health and well-being are influenced by comfort room cleanliness at Las Piñas City National Senior High School – Doña Josefa Campus

This study aims to investigate how comfort room cleanliness, including issue like water inaccessibility, vandalism, and unpleasant odors affects students focus, well-being, and satisfaction, ultimately influencing their academic engagement. Beyond documenting the challenges, it seeks to advocate for improved restroom maintenance, better school policies, and positive behavioral changes among students. Addressing these issues can create healthier, more supportive, and successful learning environments. Clean restrooms symbolize more than hygiene; they reflect how much a school values its students.

Theoretical Framework

The study titled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students" is grounded into the following theoretical perspectives:

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943)

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943), Maslow's theory emphasizes that people

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

must have their basic physiological and safety needs met before they can focus on higher-level cognitive tasks such as learning. Clean comfort rooms address essential needs for hygiene and sanitation, empowering students to feel secure and comfortable in their learning environment. In terms of application of this theory in the study, When comfort rooms are clean and functional, students' physiological and safety needs are fulfilled. This promotes a healthy, positive, and conducive learning environment by eliminating distractions caused by discomfort or health concerns.

Fletcher B. Dressler's School Hygiene Theory (1913)

Fletcher B. Dressler's School Hygiene Theory highlights the importance of maintaining hygiene and sanitation within school environments to promote students' health and academic performance. According to Dressler, maintaining clean and hygienic facilities within schools helps reduce health risks, enhance students' comfort, and improve their ability to focus on learning. In the context of this study, the School Hygiene Theory supports the idea that clean comfort rooms contribute positively to students' physical and mental well-being, thereby fostering better academic engagement and satisfaction.

Conceptual Framework

Key Variables and Their Relationships:

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Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

The framework illustrates the relationship between the Predictor (Independent) Variable which is The Comfort Room Cleanliness, while the Criterion (Dependent) Variable is the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students, which includes the student satisfaction, comfort, focus, concentration, health and well-being. This study aims to investigate the relationship between the cleanliness of comfort rooms and the academic engagement of senior high school students. Specifically, it aims to determine how hygienic conditions, proper waste disposal, and the availability of cleaning supplies in comfort rooms contribute to student's satisfaction, comfort, concentration, and overall academic engagement. The cleanliness of comfort rooms is hypothesized to influence the academic engagement of students by creating a conducive environment that supports their well-being and focus, ultimately affecting their academic performance and satisfaction with school facilities. This research could potentially guide future campus hygiene initiatives.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the impact of comfort room cleanliness on the academic engagement of senior high school student of Las Piñas National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

- 1) What is the measured level of cleanliness of the comfort rooms in the campus based on the ratings of senior high school students?

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

- 2) How does the perceived cleanliness correlate with the following aspects of student academic engagement?
 - a) Student satisfaction and comfort
 - b) Student focus and concentration
 - c) Student health and well-being

- 3) Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of comfort room cleanliness and overall student academic engagement?

Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between comfort room cleanliness and the academic engagement of senior high school students.

Significance of the Study

This study aims to provide valuable insights into how the cleanliness of comfort rooms impacts the academic engagement of senior high school students. The findings will benefit the following:

Students

This study emphasizes the importance of clean facilities for their comfort, focus, and academic engagement by highlighting how cleanliness in comfort rooms contributes to their academic engagement and learning experiences. The results may encourage students to advocate for and maintain hygienic practices in shared spaces.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Teachers

The study highlights how environmental factors, like clean comfort rooms, affect students' focus and behavior. Gaining awareness of how comfort room conditions may influence student's attention, participation and engagement in class. Teachers can see how maintaining cleanliness creates a better learning environment, helping students perform better in class.

School Administration

The research provides valuable insights for administrators regarding the role of comfort room cleanliness in shaping students' learning environments. These insights can inform strategies for improving facility maintenance to enhance students' academic experiences and overall well-being.

Staff

This study is important for school staff, especially custodians and administrators, as it shows how clean comfort rooms affect students' learning. It helps staff see their role in making school better, highlighting the importance of maintaining cleanliness for student well-being and productivity. The findings can guide staff in improving cleaning routines, managing resources, and ensuring hygiene. It reminds them their efforts help students feel comfortable and ready to learn.

Local Government Units (LGU)

The findings of this study can help the local government unit (LGU) develop policies and programs that prioritize comfort room cleanliness in schools. By understanding its impact on students' learning experiences and academic engagement, LGUs can allocate resources effectively and ensure hygienic school environments that support student's well-being and academic success.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Future Researchers

This study will assist future researchers to develop the insight gained in this study and contribute a deeper understanding about the comfort rooms in student's wellbeing. This study will also serve as reference for studies related to school hygiene, learning experience, academic engagement, academic performance,, and student comfort and wellbeing

Scope and Delimitation

This study examines the influence of comfort room cleanliness on the academic engagement of senior high school students at Las Pinas City National Senior High School – Dona Josefa Campus, for the school year 2024-2025. The scope of this study focuses on how comfort room cleanliness affects student satisfaction and comfort, their ability to focus and concentrate in class, and in their overall health and well-being. The Research explores student's perceptions of these factors and how they related to their academic engagement. This study is limited to student perspectives and does not consider other factors such as comfort room building design, and teacher perspectives. The findings aim to provide insights into improving school comfort room conditions to enhance student engagement and overall well-being.

Definition of Terms

This section gives clear, concise, and operational definitions of key concepts, variables, and terminologies used throughout the study. The terms are well-defined in place, considering their measurement or applicable application in the research to ensure that the readers have a very coherent and accurate understanding that will help eliminate confusion and bring clarity.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Comfort Room Cleanliness: This is the observed condition of cleanliness and hygiene within toilets or restrooms, which could be measured through factors such as cleanliness of the floor, walls, toilets, and sinks and the availability of essential supplies, such as soap, water, and toilet paper.

Academic Engagement: In this study, academic engagement refers to the level of student's participation, attentiveness, and overall involvement in their learning activities, as influenced by the cleanliness of the comfort rooms. It is measured through students' perceived satisfaction and comfort, ability to focus and concentrate, and overall health and well-being, using a Likert scale survey.

Senior High School Students: Specifically refers to students enrolled in Grades 11 and 12, as defined by the academic structure of the institution under study.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents a review of the literature on the impact of comfort room cleanliness on the learning experiences of senior high school students. The review identifies both positive and negative findings, providing a comprehensive understanding of how comfort room cleanliness impacts student well-being, academic engagement, and satisfaction. By analyzing these studies, we point to establish the importance of cleanliness in educational situations and its potential effect on students' academic experience.

The Importance of Comfort Room Cleanliness in Educational Environments

The cleanliness of comfort rooms plays an important role in keeping up a healthy, safe, and comfortable environment for students. Numerous studies have emphasized that cleanliness in schools, particularly in comfort rooms, contains a noteworthy impact on student well-being, satisfaction, and academic performance. Reyes et al. (2024) highlight that the cleanliness of school facilities, including comfort rooms, contributes to student satisfaction, which in turn, positively impacts academic achievement. Their findings propose that a clean and well-maintained learning environment fosters better student performance.

Additionally, Aamir (2024) emphasize that clean restrooms reduce uneasiness and promote hygiene, creating a healthier and more conducive learning environment. These factors, according to the study, support students' academic success by reducing

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

distractions and promoting better physical and mental wellbeing.

Particularly, Kabir et al. (2021) present a negative view, showing how insufficient cleanliness in school facilities, especially restrooms, negatively impacts students' satisfaction, academic performance, and overall well-being. The study calls attention to the need for regular cleaning and proper sanitation to maintain a conducive learning environment.

Also, Duijster et al. (2022) further emphasize this need, stating that clean restrooms are essential for students' wellbeing which significant resources must be allocated to cleanliness activities in schools.

Adding to the positive perspective, Abney et al. (2020) Explore the relationship between cleanliness and student satisfaction in higher education institutions. They found that a direct positive correlation exists between clean restrooms and overall student satisfaction, suggesting that the state of school facilities especially in comfort rooms plays a significant role in forming students' perceptions of their learning environment.

Moreover, Uleanya et al. (2021) examine the impact of clean restrooms on student health and well-being, emphasizing that maintaining hygienic conditions reduces absenteeism and supports academic performance. Their study advocates for regular cleaning schedules and the involvement of students in maintaining cleanliness to ensure a safe and healthy learning environment.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Similarly, Vanguard (2024) emphasizes the critical role of school cleanliness in improving student performance by creating a healthy, focused, and productive learning environment. The study highlights that clean facilities significantly reduce absenteeism by mitigating health risks associated with poor hygiene. Additionally, factors such as proper ventilation, temperature control, and accessible hygiene practices are identified as essential for fostering a conducive academic atmosphere. Cleanliness not only promotes physical health but also enhances cognitive engagement, affirming its positive impact on overall student outcomes.

Additionally, Courterior et al. (2020) also support the positive connection between cleanliness and student satisfaction, emphasizing that students' perceptions of cleanliness are directly affected by the physical state of comfort rooms. Their study shows that clean restrooms contribute to a feeling of safety and well-being, which in turn improves student's overall satisfaction with their school environment.

Also, Wang et al. (2021) explore the broader impacts of facility cleanliness on student's mental health, as the study conclude that maintaining clean school facilities, including comfort rooms, plays an important role in reducing stress and uneasiness among students, thus positively impacting their academic engagement.

Similarly, Shao (2020) emphasizes how cleanliness can establish a positive setting for learning. Their study focusing on public facilities reflects that cleanliness matters are not only influential in user satisfaction but also in his emotional state; this emotional state further influences student attitudes toward his educational activities.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Also, Adewusi and Oguntokun (2024) highlight the critical role of accessible and well-maintained comfort rooms in fostering a healthy and conducive learning environment. Their study reveals that the poor state of sanitary facilities in a major academic institution in South West Nigeria negatively impacts student well-being, hygiene, and overall school experience. With a student-to-toilet ratio of 1:195—far exceeding recommended standards—students face significant challenges in accessing clean and functional restrooms. The study further identifies key factors influencing restroom utilization, including proper lighting, ventilation, water supply, privacy, security, accessibility for disabled individuals, and clear signage. Many restrooms remain locked or inadequately maintained, leading to unhygienic practices such as open defecation, which poses serious health risks. These findings emphasize the urgent need for institutions to prioritize restroom accessibility, regular maintenance, and proper sanitation measures to support student health, comfort, and academic engagement. Ensuring the availability of clean and accessible comfort rooms not only improves hygiene but also contributes to a more positive and productive educational environment.

Not only that, Okoro et al. (2020) highlight how essential water is in keeping school restrooms clean and functional. Their study found that while most restrooms were well-maintained, a temporary lack of water led to a noticeable decline in hygiene. This shows that without a steady water supply, maintaining proper sanitation becomes a challenge, creating an uncomfortable and unhealthy environment for students. Poor restroom conditions can be distracting and even harmful to student well-being, making it harder to focus on learning.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

The study reinforces the need for consistent water access and proper facility management to ensure restrooms remain clean, safe, and supportive of a positive educational experience.

Additionally, Istichomah and Astuti (2023) emphasize the importance of maintaining proper sanitation facilities and ensuring regular cleaning of school facilities, such as comfort rooms, to promote student well-being and create a conducive learning environment. The authors argue that a clean environment supports students physical and mental wellbeing, improving their focus and engagement in academic activities. Furthermore, the study underscores that proper cleaning practices and a systematic approach to restroom maintenance can improve both student satisfaction and academic outcomes.

In addition, Dagoc (2020) conducted a study to evaluate the level of student satisfaction with restroom facilities at Saint Michael College of Caraga. The research utilized a descriptive design and survey method to identify critical factors influencing restroom satisfaction, specifically cleanliness, fragrance, and overall space. The findings showed that even though most students expressed satisfaction with the current state of the restrooms, Cleanliness was the main issue identified by those students, besides complaints about bad fragrance and inadequate space. The study emphasized that restroom conditions play an important role in shaping students experiences within the school environment. To address these issues and improve overall satisfaction, Dagoc suggested implementing proper monitoring systems and prioritizing improvements in restroom management. These enhancements aim to promote a cleaner, more

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

comfortable, and student-friendly atmosphere, ultimately contributing to a better educational environment.

Moreover, Qadeer et al. (2024) highlighted the importance of well-maintained school facilities in impacting students learning experiences and academic outcomes. The authors found a very strong positive relationship between the quality of school facilities, such as classrooms and comfort rooms, and student satisfaction. Satisfaction, along with supportive comfort room environments characterized by security and mutual respect, enhances academic performance. The conclusion of the research recommends investment in school infrastructures to promote a pleasant environment conducive to learning while presenting the holistic effects that cleanliness and facility maintenance have on student well-being and success.

Also, Thompson S. (2023) emphasizes that maintaining clean and well-equipped school washrooms is essential for fostering a positive learning environment. Proper hygiene facilities help reduce the spread of illnesses, enhance student comfort, and support emotional well-being, all of which contribute to students' ability to focus and participate in academic activities. Additionally, well-maintained restrooms promote privacy, dignity, and inclusivity by ensuring accessibility for all students, creating a supportive atmosphere that encourages academic engagement. Schools that prioritize restroom cleanliness demonstrate a commitment to student welfare, positively influencing school culture, reputation, and overall student experience. Furthermore, integrating hygiene education within restroom spaces reinforces proper sanitation habits among students. These insights align with the broader understanding that cleanliness in educational environments directly

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

impacts student satisfaction, health, and academic engagement, highlighting the necessity of high sanitation standards in schools.

Furthermore, Sharma et al. (2024) emphasize that the quality of WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) facilities, including the cleanliness of school restrooms, significantly affects students' health, attendance, and academic performance. Poor sanitation, especially the absence of proper facilities for menstruating girls, leads to higher absenteeism and reduced focus in class. The study concludes that improving comfort room cleanliness and overall hygiene in schools is essential to enhancing students' learning experience and overall educational achievement.

However, Palar et al. (2022) indicate that inadequate sanitation management in public institutions, such as government schools, results in poor hygiene and cleanliness, which can negatively affect user satisfaction and health. The absence of proper sanitation facilities and dedicated management for cleanliness in these settings points to the need for improvement. In contrast, the present study aims to explore how maintaining cleanliness in school comfort rooms positively influences student learning experiences, thus, highlighting the gap in addressing sanitation issues and its broader implications on educational settings.

Nevertheless, Baafi (2020) emphasized the critical role of the school physical environment in shaping academic performance among senior high school students. The study showed that students who were in schools with a well-maintained and conducive learning environment always performed better academically than those who were in less favorable conditions. Adequate school facilities, clean and functional spaces, were cited

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

as key contributors to fostering a positive educational climate and improving student learning. This study supports the notion that cleanliness and maintenance of school facilities, including comfort rooms, are essential in creating an environment that fosters academic success and overall student well-being. This therefore aligns with the importance of comfort room cleanliness, suggesting that well-maintained facilities contribute to a conducive learning experience for students.

The Role of Cleanliness in Student's Academic Engagement and Well-being

Clean comfort rooms are not only important for student's health but also for their engagement and behavior within the school environment. When students perceive their surroundings to be clean and well-maintained, they are more likely to engage positively in their academic task

According to the School of Scholars (2023), a clean school environment essentially improves student health, focus, and academic performance. Clean restrooms reduce the spread of germs, in this manner minimizing illnesses and absenteeism, which ensures that students can participate fully in their academic activities. Furthermore, a clean and organized space promotes a sense of calm and safety, reduces anxiety, and enhances students' ability to concentrate on their studies. Proper cleaning also promotes good indoor air quality, hence supporting student's respiratory health, which improves students' abilities to perform to the best of their capacities in school. Keeping school facilities, especially comfort rooms and public areas clean impacts the student's physical and mental well-being and in this way contributes to better focus and engagement.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Besides the short-term gains, cleanliness in schools creates a long-term culture of personal cleanliness and environmental stewardship. Through incorporating sanitation practices and maintainability activities such as hand-washing campaigns, recycling programs, and effective waste management systems, schools instill values that extend beyond the confines of the comfort rooms. In conclusion, cleaning up school facilities is not just cleanliness but an important factor in making a safe, healthy, and supportive environment in learning. Efforts that keep the schools clean improve student involvement, wellness, and achievement while developing behavior that promotes long-term personal and social growth.

Also, Magpusao et al. (2020) established that the availability of cleaning materials and the support of student cooperation in maintaining cleanliness are effective strategies for improving the overall cleanliness of school restrooms. The study conducted on Grade 12 students at Bestlink College demonstrates how providing students with the necessary tools to maintain cleanliness can help make a more secure and more comfortable school environment. Students dynamic support in maintaining cleanliness develops a sense of responsibility and cooperation, which in turn can lead to more positive engagement in learning activities.

Moreover, Doubek (2021) supports this view by stating the role of student behavior in terms of comfort room cleanliness. The author stated that if the schools can encourage responsible behaviors, such as proper waste disposal and regular cleaning, they can minimize vandalism and other undesirable behaviors. This contributes to a more positive and conducive learning environment.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Similarly, Shaughnessy et al. (2022) also point to the need for cleanliness in student health and attendance. The author of this study argue that clean comfort rooms prevent the outbreak of infectious diseases, thus eliminating student absences and encouraging students to participate actively in school affairs. Clean facilities are therefore fundamental to ensuring students stay healthy and engaged in their studies. This study indicates that hygiene has a direct impact on attendance, as students are less likely to miss school due to health concerns emerging from poor hygiene practices.

Also, Yonash (2020) highlights the critical link between restroom sanitation and student health and engagement. The study reveals that unsanitary school restrooms can lead to the spread of illness, increased absenteeism, and diminished focus among students, all of which negatively impact their overall well-being and academic success. Poor restroom conditions often discourage students from utilizing the facilities, leading to discomfort and distraction during classes. This underscores the importance of maintaining clean and well-equipped restrooms to support student health, foster engagement, and create an environment conducive to learning.

Additionally, Restroom cleanliness significantly influences the health and learning experiences of students. Thao et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of maintaining hygienic restrooms in schools through innovative methods, such as integrating Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) predictive models. These systems collect real-time data on ammonia (NH_3) concentrations and relative humidity (RH), enabling timely cleaning interventions and ensuring hygienic conditions. Unhygienic restrooms are often linked to health issues, such as the spread of infections,

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

which can result in increased absenteeism and reduced academic performance. By addressing restroom conditions proactively, schools can create a safer and more conducive environment for learning. The study by Le Quang et al. highlights how advanced monitoring systems can effectively mitigate these risks, ensuring student well-being and enhancing the overall learning experience.

Moreover, Cha et al. (2020) also conduct studies on the school sanitation and overall engagement of students. The author of the study stated that well-maintained restrooms contribute to a positive learning environment by reducing stressors that can detract from students focus on academic tasks. This study suggests that the cleanliness of school facilities directly correlates with students ability to concentrate and perform better in their studies.

However, Moreira et al. (2020) broaden the discussion by recommending that cleanliness should be viewed in conjunction with other factors such as leadership support and authoritative practices. Their study demonstrates that while cleanliness is a critical factor, it should be part of an all-encompassing approach to improving school environments. They emphasize that leadership and staff involvement in maintaining cleanliness, alongside regular cleaning schedules, are key to making a supportive and effective learning environment.

Additionally, Vos and Galetzka (2020) offer a different perspective, challenging the commonly held belief that cleanliness directly impacts student learning. Their study suggests that students' perceptions of cleanliness are often shaped more by emotional and social factors than by the actual condition of the facilities. They argue that while

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

cleanliness may impact student behavior, the emotional responses and social dynamics surrounding the learning environment may play an even more significant role. According to their research, improvements in cleanliness alone are insufficient unless accompanied by broader contextual changes, such as addressing social dynamics and environmental cues.

Also, Estacio and Gopez (2021) address concerns regarding the cleanliness of comfort rooms in schools, particularly at Bulacan State University. Their study focuses on cleaning methods and communication systems but does not fully investigate how restroom cleanliness impacts students learning experiences beyond just satisfaction. They emphasize the importance of improving cleaning procedures and communication channels to ensure proper cleanliness. However, their study overlooks broader factors such as the overall facility design, hygiene education, and regulatory support, which are key to making lasting improvements in the school environment.

But on the other hand, Sunga (2023) conducted a study at Sta. Cruz Elementary School in Antipolo to evaluate the implementation of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WaSH) program and its relationship with the hygiene and sanitation practices of intermediate pupils. Using a descriptive correlational research design, the study included 85 teachers and 362 pupils from Grades IV to VI. The findings revealed a high level of WaSH program implementation, particularly in promoting disease prevention and community health, as perceived by both teachers and pupils. Notably, the study identified a significant relationship between the program's implementation and the pupils' hygiene practices.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

By fostering proper hygiene habits, the WaSH program not only contributes to improved health outcomes but also positively influences students' learning experiences. Healthier pupils are better equipped to engage in academic activities, demonstrating enhanced focus, reduced absenteeism, and greater overall academic performance. The study concludes that further improvements in WaSH program management can create a more conducive environment for learning by addressing both health and hygiene needs.

Alternatively, while Azmi et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of cleanliness in public restrooms for users' comfort and well-being, their study primarily focuses on commercial spaces rather than educational settings. The findings of their study, while relevant to common cleanliness practices, do not directly translate to the school environment, where the focus is on improving student learning rather than client satisfaction in public spaces. This presents a limitation in applying their results to the educational context, which requires a focus on factors such as student engagement, academic performance, and the effect of cleanliness on learning.

Also, Casperson (2024) highlights the critical role of school restroom cleanliness in maintaining student health, satisfaction, and academic success. Unsanitary restrooms can negatively impact students' perceptions of their school, discourage restroom use, and increase the spread of germs, ultimately affecting their well-being and focus in class. A lack of clean and well-maintained facilities can lead to discomfort, distractions, and absenteeism, all of which hinder students' ability to fully engage in their academic tasks. To address these concerns, the implementation of touchless fixtures, such as sensor-operated faucets and flush valves, is recommended to minimize germ transmission.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Additionally, restroom designs should allow users to exit without touching doors to further reduce bacterial spread. Proper maintenance, regular cleaning, and effective ventilation are essential in preventing unpleasant odors and maintaining hygiene standards. School restroom sanitation should be a top priority, as a well-maintained facility contributes to a positive school environment and supports students' overall success. A clean and hygienic school building enhances student satisfaction and fosters a conducive atmosphere for learning by promoting focus, comfort, and well-being. Students who have access to clean restrooms are less likely to experience stress or anxiety related to poor hygiene conditions, allowing them to concentrate better on their studies. Furthermore, improved restroom conditions provide a sense of security and dignity, making students feel more comfortable in their school environment. To achieve this, schools should adopt strict sanitation practices, including the use of disinfectants, installation of no-touch garbage bins, and continuous promotion of proper handwashing. Additionally, reinforcing school morale and student responsibility can discourage vandalism and help sustain restroom cleanliness. By prioritizing hygiene and maintenance, schools can create a healthier and more supportive educational setting that enhances student engagement, academic performance, and overall well-being.

Furthermore, Canoog et al. (2024) emphasize the importance of maintaining comfortable and accessible restroom facilities in educational institutions and their impact on student academic engagement. Their study at Cebu Technological University- Pinamungajan Campus highlights how restroom cleanliness, privacy, hygiene standards, and accessibility contribute to a positive campus environment.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Comfort plays a crucial role in restroom usability, ensuring that facilities are clean, well-maintained, and properly equipped. Accessibility further promotes inclusivity by ensuring restrooms accommodate diverse needs, including individuals with disabilities. By actively engaging with the campus community, the study identifies key challenges and areas for improvement, reinforcing the need for institutions to prioritize restroom maintenance and accessibility. Providing well-maintained facilities not only enhances student well-being but also supports academic engagement by reducing distractions, discomfort, and health-related absenteeism. A clean and accessible restroom environment enables students to focus better on their studies, fostering a more productive and supportive educational experience.

Synthesis

The cleanliness of school comfort rooms has long been recognized as an important factor that affects students' learning experiences. Many studies have shown that the condition of hygiene facilities has both direct and indirect effects on students' well-being, engagement, and academic performance. Research (Reyes et al., 2024; Aamir, 2024; Abney et al., 2020) highlights that clean, well-maintained comfort rooms contribute to student satisfaction, reduce distractions, and improve academic success by creating a healthier and more comfortable environment. These findings are supported by studies from (Uleanya et al., 2021; Vanguard, 2024), which emphasize that sanitary facilities help lower absenteeism and health risks, making it easier for students to consistently participate in class. Similarly, (Yonash, 2020; Courterior et al., 2020) stress that poor

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

comfort room conditions negatively impact students' ability to focus, their behavior, and overall well-being, further proving the importance of maintaining proper hygiene.

However, some studies take a different approach. (Vos and Galetzka, 2020; Moreira et al., 2020) argue that emotional and social factors, not just hygiene, shape how students perceive cleanliness, suggesting that broader improvements in school environments are needed. (Moreira et al., 2020) also propose that integrating cleanliness into leadership practices could offer a more complete approach to improving school facilities. Additionally, (Dagoc, 2020) points out that issues such as bad odors and cramped spaces in comfort rooms play a key role in students' satisfaction with cleanliness, while (Istichomah and Astuti, 2023; Sharma et al., 2024) note that broader WASH programs can improve hygiene and lead to better academic outcomes by addressing health concerns.

Innovative strategies for maintaining hygiene have also been explored. For instance, (Thao et al., 2023) demonstrate how using Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) can help tackle hygiene problems before they escalate, reducing health risks and making the learning environment more effective. In the same way, (Sunga, 2023; Palar et al., 2022) stress the importance of systematic sanitation practices and regulatory support to maintain high hygiene standards. Despite the valuable insights provided by these studies, several research gaps remain. One major gap is conceptual, as pointed out by (Vos and Galetzka, 2020), where more attention is needed on how emotional and social factors shape students' views of cleanliness, beyond just the physical aspects of hygiene. Most research to date has focused mainly on the visible side of cleanliness, without fully exploring how students' perceptions are influenced by their broader social

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

environment. There is also an empirical gap because many studies rely on correlational data and do not provide clear, direct evidence that links specific comfort room conditions to academic performance (Dagoc, 2020; Reyes et al., 2024).

Additionally, a theoretical gap exists, as there is a lack of strong, theory-driven models that explain how comfort room cleanliness affects both academic performance and student well-being (Moreira et al., 2020). Methodologically, most studies use descriptive or cross-sectional designs, but more in-depth longitudinal research would help better understand how comfort room conditions affect students' engagement and academic outcomes over time.

Therefore, while the evidence shows that the cleanliness of school comfort rooms is an important factor in students' learning experiences, more research is needed to address these conceptual, empirical, theoretical, and methodological gaps. Future studies should examine how emotional and social influences shape perceptions of cleanliness, establish stronger links between cleanliness and academic performance, develop theory-based models, and use long-term research methods. This will lead to a fuller understanding of the role hygiene plays in education and contribute to creating a better learning environment for students.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter explains the research methods used in the study to ensure a reliable way of collecting and analyzing data. It starts with a description of the research design, which is then used to conduct the study. The methods for choosing participants, including the population and sampling technique, are discussed, along with a brief description of the respondents. The chapter also details the tools for data collection, including validation and reliability testing. It explains the steps for accurate and relevant information gathering, as well as the statistical methods for data analysis. Lastly, it addresses the ethical considerations followed to respect participants' rights.

Research Design

This study employed a Descriptive–Correlational Research Design to examine how senior high school students perceived the cleanliness of comfort rooms and its potential impact on their health, focus, and academic success. The descriptive component of the design assessed students' perceptions and satisfaction with the cleanliness of the comfort rooms. Meanwhile, the correlational aspect investigated whether a relationship existed between comfort room cleanliness and key outcomes, such as student satisfaction, comfort, focus, concentration, and health and well-being. The study sought to identify meaningful connections between comfort room cleanliness and academic engagement. By exploring these relationships, the study aimed to highlight how environmental factors, such as cleanliness, might influence students' academic abilities. The Descriptive–Correlational Research Design was supported by Best and Kahn (1972) in *Research in Education*, which

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

emphasizes that correlational studies can determine the degree of relationship between variables in educational settings, although they do not confirm direct causation.

Population and Sampling Technique

This study used convenience sampling to select participants. The study focused on Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus, and data were collected from students in different grade levels, academic strands, and sections. Participants were chosen based on their availability and whether they met the study's criteria. This method ensured that the study gathered opinions from a variety of senior high school students, while also considering practical limits during data collection. The sample size was based on the number of students who were available and willing to join during the data collection period, making sure it was large enough for reliable analysis. This approach helped gather useful information about how students viewed the cleanliness of comfort rooms and its possible effect on their learning.

Respondents of the study

The study collected information from 307 students enrolled at Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus. These students came from Grade 11 and Grade 12 and were distributed across various strands, such as GAS (General Academic Strand), TVL-HE (Home Economics), TVL-ICT (Information and Communications Technology), and ABM (Accountancy, Business, and Management). Respondents were selected based on specific criteria: they had to be currently enrolled, available during the data collection period, and regular users of the campus comfort rooms. This ensured that the feedback was relevant to the study's objective of understanding how comfort room cleanliness affected the academic engagement of senior high school students. The sample size of 307 was determined based on

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

the population size of 1,524 students. Using the Raosoft sample size calculator, it was found that at least 306.69 respondents were required to achieve a 5% margin of error with a 95% confidence level. To ensure reliability, the sample size was rounded up to 307 respondents, providing sufficient representation to gather diverse perspectives while maintaining accuracy in the study's findings.

Instrumentation

For this study, the researchers used researcher-made survey questionnaires as the primary tool for gathering information. The survey questionnaire consisted of over 40 items. The questionnaire was designed to capture the perspectives of senior high school students regarding the cleanliness of comfort rooms and how this influenced their academic engagement. The questions aimed to explore several key areas, focusing on how the state of the comfort rooms affected the students' academic experiences. The first part of the survey measured students' perceptions of comfort room cleanliness. This helped the researchers understand how students rated the cleanliness of the comfort rooms in their school. The next section examined how the cleanliness of these spaces affected different aspects of their academic engagement, including their overall satisfaction and comfort, as well as the impact on their concentration and focus during class. Additionally, the survey explored how the condition of the comfort rooms impacted students' health and well-being, particularly in relation to hygiene concerns and the risk of illness from unclean environments. The responses provided valuable insights into how the cleanliness of comfort rooms affected students' academic performance, their health, and their general comfort at school.

This data allowed the researchers to better understand the role that comfort room cleanliness played in shaping the overall academic engagement of senior high school students.

Validation and test of reliability of instrument

To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, it underwent a validation process by experts and teachers in the fields of education and research. Validation referred to the process of confirming that the instrument accurately measured what it was intended to measure. In this case, the questionnaire was evaluated for its relevance, clarity, and alignment with the study's objectives regarding the cleanliness of comfort rooms and its potential impact on students' academic engagement. The validation process involved gathering feedback from subject matter experts with experience in survey design and educational research. These experts assessed whether the questions were clear, relevant, and appropriately designed to capture the information needed for the study. Any suggestions for improvement or revisions were incorporated to enhance the questionnaire's effectiveness. Afterward, the approved and validated survey questionnaire underwent reliability testing using Cronbach's alpha and was pilot tested on non-respondents. By ensuring that the questionnaire was both valid and well-aligned with the research objectives, the study guaranteed that the data collected would be credible, reliable, and accurate, reflecting students' true perceptions regarding comfort room cleanliness.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the survey, the researcher asked for formal approval from the school principal of Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus to

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

gather and collect data from the students. Once approval was granted, the approved and printed questionnaires were distributed to students who met the study's criteria, selected through convenience sampling. The respondents included students from Grade 11 and Grade 12 across different strands, chosen based on their availability, current enrollment, and regular use of the campus comfort rooms. Before distributing the questionnaires, the researcher clearly explained the purpose and objectives of the research in simple, understandable terms to ensure participants were fully informed about the study. Each participant was provided with a consent form outlining their rights as participants. This emphasized that participation was entirely voluntary, that their responses would remain anonymous, and that they could withdraw from the study at any time without facing any negative consequences. All collected data was treated with strict confidentiality. The responses were recorded and securely stored, with only authorized individuals having access to the data. No identifying information was linked to individual responses to protect the privacy of participants. After collecting the completed questionnaires, the data was carefully reviewed and analyzed to address the research objectives. This process allowed the researchers to gain meaningful insights and draw conclusions that reflected the experiences and perspectives of the respondents

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected in this study were analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between the cleanliness of comfort rooms and the academic engagement of senior high school students. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to assess the degree of linear relationship between two

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

continuous variables. A coefficient value closer to +1 indicated a strong positive correlation, meaning that as one variable increased, the other also increased. A coefficient closer to -1 indicated a strong negative correlation, meaning that as one variable increased, the other decreased. A value near 0 suggested a weak or no correlation, indicating that the variables did not have a linear relationship. In this study, Pearson's correlation was specifically used to examine the relationship between students' perceptions of comfort room cleanliness and their academic experiences, including factors such as academic performance, satisfaction, and engagement. This statistical method allowed the researchers to understand how the cleanliness of comfort rooms might have influenced various aspects of students' academic lives. To assess the significance of the correlation, a significance level of 0.05 was adopted. This meant that if the resulting p-value was less than 0.05, the relationship was considered statistically significant, implying that the observed correlation was unlikely to have occurred by chance.

The following table presents the interpretation of the Pearson correlation coefficient values.:

Pearson's r value	Interpretation
0.90 to 1.00	Very Strong Positive Correlation
0.70 to 0.89	Strong Positive Correlation
0.50 to 0.69	Moderate Positive Correlation
0.30 to 0.49	Weak Positive Correlation
0.10 to 0.29	Very Weak Positive Correlation
-0.09 to 0.09	No or Negligible Correlation
-0.10 to -0.29	Very Weak Negative Correlation
-0.30 to -0.49	Weak Negative Correlation
-0.50 to -0.69	Moderate Negative Correlation
-0.70 to -0.89	Strong Negative Correlation
-0.90 to -1.00	Very Strong Negative Correlation

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

In this study, the correlation coefficient helped to clarify how strongly the cleanliness of comfort rooms was linked to students' academic experiences. The results were presented through tables and figures to facilitate a clearer understanding and comparison of findings.

This version of the statistical treatment section provided a clearer and more thorough explanation of Pearson's correlation and its application to the study. It included a structured table for interpreting Pearson's r values, which assisted in understanding the strength and direction of the relationships between the variables in this study. The table used a range of values to interpret the correlation in a more detailed way, based on the study by Wahyuni (2020).

Ethical Considerations

To protect the participants rights and well-being, it was important to make sure the study was conducted ethically. All participants were asked for their informed consent before any data were collected, ensuring they were aware of the study's goals, procedures, and potential risks. The identities of the respondents were kept confidential by ensuring that personal information remained anonymous and private. Additionally, measures were taken to reduce any potential harm, both psychologically and physically. The dignity and rights of the students were always respected, allowing them to decline or stop participating without facing any consequences. To preserve the integrity of the study, further steps were taken to ensure that the data collected was accurate and was handled appropriately.

Chapter IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter includes an overview of the collected data, an analysis and interpretation of the variables according to the listed order or research questions, and a discussion of the findings bolstered by relevant literature and emphasizing the extensive and noteworthy implications of the research.

Problem Number 1: What is the Student’s Perceived level on the cleanliness of the comfort rooms?

Table 1 Mean Responses of Student’s Perceived Level of Cleanliness of Comfort Rooms (PLC).

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
1. I find the comfort rooms in DJC generally clean.	2.34	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees;rarely observed or experience the stated condition.
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms on campus.	2.39	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees;rarely observed or experience the stated condition.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms in DJC meets Acceptable hygiene standards.	2.53	Agree	Mostly Agrees; observes the condition but with minor reservations.
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.	2.47	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees; rarely observed or experience the stated condition.
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toiletpaper) in the comfort rooms.	2.03	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees; rarely observed or experience the stated condition.
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.	2.31	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees; rarely observed or experience the stated condition.
7. I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms.	2.57	Agree	Mostly Agrees; observes the condition but with minor reservations.

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.	2.45	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees; rarely observed or experience the stated condition.
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.	2.39	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees; rarely observed or experience the stated condition.
Composite Mean	2.18	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees; rarely observed or experience the stated condition.

**Legend*

Rating	Scale Range	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Fully Agrees; consistently experiences the stated condition
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Mostly Agrees; observes the condition but with minor reservations
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Somewhat Disagrees; rarely observed or experience the stated condition
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Completely Disagrees; does not observe or experience the stated condition

The Students' Perceived Level of Cleanliness is shown in the table. The indicators, respondents' mean ratings, composite mean, descriptive rating, and verbal interpretation are all included each table. Using Microsoft Excel and Google Sheets, the mean rating of

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

respondents are calculated and averaged to get the overall rating, specific descriptive ratings are offered along with appropriate verbal interpretation. This Table Consist of the indicators, mean rating of the respondents, descriptive rating, and verbal interpretations.

Table 1 shows Item number 7, which states, 'I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms,' obtained the highest mean score of 2.57, indicating a 'disagree' rating with a verbal interpretation of "somewhat disagree; noticing the issue but perceiving little impact."

In Item number 5, which states, "I notice there are enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms,' obtained the lowest mean score of 2.03, indicating a 'disagree' rating with a verbal interpretation of 'somewhat disagree; noticing the issue but perceiving little impact."

The mean responses of Student's Perceived level of cleanliness of Comfort Rooms is 2.18, has a descriptive rating of "Disagree", and has a verbal interpretation of "Somewhat Disagrees; rarely observe or experiences the stated condition" This suggest that on average, respondents recognize concerns regarding the cleanliness and maintenance of the comfort rooms but may also not view them as significantly affecting their overall experiences. Studies emphasizes that maintaining hygienic comfort rooms is essential for student's well-being, as it impacts their comfort. Health, and academic engagement (Istichomah & Astuti, 2023; Thao et al., 2023). The findings highlight the need for improved cleanliness, regular maintenance, and adequate hygiene and cleaning

supplies to enhance the overall restroom experience in the campus resulting for better academic engagements students.

Problem Number 2: How does the perceived cleanliness correlate with the following aspects of student academic engagement?

- a) **Student satisfaction and comfort**
- b) **Student focus and concentration**
- c) **Student health and well-being**

Table 2.1 Mean Responses on Student Satisfaction and Comfort (ISC).

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
1. feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean	3.33	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.	3.36	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.	3.19	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean	3.29	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
5. I always prefer to use a clean restroom, even if a dirty one is easier to access.	3.37	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
6. I feel respected as a student when I see that the comfort rooms are well-maintained.	3.44	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
7. I believe that clean comfort rooms show the school's commitment to student well-being.	3.47	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
8. I feel that my overall satisfaction with school facilities depends on the cleanliness of the comfort rooms.	3.27	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
9. I believe that clean comfort rooms improve my overall school experience	3.19	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
10. I think that dirty restrooms negatively impact my perception of the school.	3.31	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
Composite Mean	3.32	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement

**Legend:*

Rating	Scale Range	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25- 4.00	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
3	2.50– 3.24	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
2	1.75– 2.49	Disagree	Partially disagrees with the statement
1	1.00- 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Completely disagrees with the statement

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

The table presents the Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on Students Satisfaction and Comfort. The tables consist of the indicators, mean rating of respondents, descriptive rating, and verbal interpretation. Using Microsoft Excel and Google Sheets, the mean rating of respondents is calculated and averaged to get the overall rating, specific descriptive ratings are offered along with appropriate verbal interpretation.

Table 2.1 shows Item number 7, which states, "I believe that clean comfort rooms show the school's commitment to student well-being," obtained the highest mean score of 3.46, indicating a 'Strongly Agree' rating with a verbal interpretation of "Completely agrees with the statement."

Item number 9, which states, "I believe that clean comfort rooms improve my overall school experience," obtained the lowest mean score of 3.19, indicating a 'Agree' rating with a verbal interpretation of "Partially agrees with the statement."

The mean responses on comfort room cleanliness impact on student satisfaction and comfort is 3.32, which has a Strongly Agree descriptive rating and a verbal interpretation of "Completely agrees with the statement." This suggests that, overall, respondents fully agree that comfort room cleanliness impacts their satisfaction and comfort in school. Research supports this positive relationship between cleanliness and student satisfaction. Reyes et al. (2024) highlight that cleanliness contributes to student satisfaction, which, in turn, positively affects academic achievement. Similarly, Courterior et al. (2020) argue that the physical state of comfort rooms directly impacts student

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

satisfaction by fostering a feeling of safety and well-being. Azmi et al. (2023) further emphasize that cleanliness in comfort rooms is important for users' comfort, aligning with the students' experiences of comfort rooms on campus. Although cleanliness is a key factor, Kabir et al. (2021) stress that regular cleaning and proper sanitation are necessary to maintain a conducive learning environment, which highlights the importance of ongoing efforts to meet student needs.

The findings clearly indicate that students recognize the importance of comfort room cleanliness in their overall satisfaction and comfort within the school environment. A high agreement level suggests that cleanliness not only influences their well-being but also contributes to a more positive learning experience. When comfort rooms are well-maintained, students feel safer, more at ease, and less distracted by hygiene concerns, allowing them to focus better on their studies. However, cleanliness alone is not enough. Consistent sanitation efforts and maintenance are necessary to sustain this positive impact. Without proper upkeep, the benefits of a clean restroom may diminish over time, potentially affecting student satisfaction and comfort. Schools should therefore implement regular cleaning schedules and hygiene initiatives to maintain an environment that supports student well-being and learning.

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Table 2.2 Mean Responses on Student Focus and Concentration (IFC).

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
1. I find it easier to focus in class when the comfort rooms are clean	3.17	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
2. I prefer using the comfort rooms when they are clean during school hours.	3.33	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
3. I feel more focused on my studies after using A clean comfort room.	3.19	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
4 I feel more at ease during class when the comfort rooms are clean.	3.21	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
5. I feel more prepared to participate in class activities after using a clean restroom.	3.14	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
6. I feel that clean comfort rooms help me concentrate better in lessons.	3.12	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
7. I feel more engaged in class discussions after using a well-maintained restroom	3.20	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
8. I believe that the cleanliness of the comfort rooms positively affects my attentiveness during lectures.	3.19	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
9. I find it easier to concentrate in school when I know the restrooms are well-maintained.	3.21	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
10. I believe that regular cleaning of the comfort rooms helps me stay focused on my studies	3.19	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
Composite Mean	3.20	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement

**Legend*

Rating	Scale Range	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree	Partially disagrees with the statement
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Completely disagrees with the statement

The table presents the Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on Students Focus and Concentration. The tables consist of the indicators, mean rating of respondents, descriptive rating, and verbal interpretation. Using Microsoft Excel and Google Sheets, the mean rating of respondents is calculated and averaged to get the overall rating, specific descriptive ratings are offered along with appropriate verbal interpretation.

Table 2.2 shows Item number 2, which states, "I prefer using the comfort rooms when they are clean during school hours," obtained the highest mean score of 3.33,

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

indicating a Strongly Agree rating with the verbal interpretation of "Completely agrees with the statement."

Item number 6, which states, "I feel that clean comfort rooms help me concentrate better in lessons," obtained the lowest mean score of 3.12, indicating an Agree rating with the verbal interpretation of "Partially agrees with the statement."

The mean response on the impact of comfort room cleanliness on student focus and concentration is 3.20, which falls under the "Agree" category, with a verbal interpretation of "Partially agrees with the statement." This suggests that, overall, respondents somewhat agree that the cleanliness of comfort rooms positively affects their ability to focus and concentrate in school. Research supports this relationship, as Shao (2020) emphasizes how cleanliness creates a positive emotional environment that reduces stress and enhances focus. Qadeer et al. (2024) also highlight the strong connection between well-maintained school facilities, including comfort rooms, and improved student satisfaction, which in turn positively impacts focus and academic performance. Baafi (2020) reinforces this idea, indicating that clean and functional school facilities are essential for fostering a conducive learning environment and improving student focus. Cha et al. (2020) further support this, noting that clean restrooms contribute to reduced stress and better concentration on academic tasks.

The research highlights a clear connection between cleanliness and students' emotional well-being, focus, and academic performance. A clean environment fosters a sense of comfort and reduces stress, allowing students to concentrate better on their studies. Well-maintained school facilities, including restrooms, play a crucial role in shaping a positive learning atmosphere where students feel at ease and supported.

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

When students have access to clean and functional restrooms, they are less likely to be distracted by discomfort or hygiene concerns, leading to improved satisfaction and academic engagement. This underscores the importance of maintaining cleanliness as a fundamental aspect of a conducive learning environment. Schools should prioritize regular upkeep and hygiene initiatives to ensure that students can focus on their education without unnecessary distractions.

Table 2.3 Mean Responses on Student Health and Well-Being (IHW).

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
1. I believe that clean restrooms contribute positively to my physical health and well-being at school.	3.53	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
2. I feel confident that the cleanliness of the restrooms helps prevent health issues for students.	3.48	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
3. I feel less stressed during school hours when I know the comfort rooms are clean.	3.29	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4. I believe that clean restrooms promote good mental well-being.	3.35	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
5. I feel that using a clean restroom helps me avoid illness or infections.	3.46	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
6. I feel at ease knowing that the hygiene standards in the comfort rooms meet my needs	3.44	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
7. I believe that maintaining hygiene in restrooms is essential for promoting student health	3.49	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
8. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better overall health for students.	3.50	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement

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Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
9. I feel safer using a clean restroom compared to an unclean one	3.52	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
10. I feel motivated to maintain better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean	3.51	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
Composite Mean	3.46	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement

**Legend*

Rating	Scale Range	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Completely agrees with the statement
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree	Partially agrees with the statement
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree	Partially disagrees with the statement
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Completely disagrees with the statement

The table presents the Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on Students Health and Well-Being. The tables consist of the indicators, mean rating of respondents, descriptive rating, and verbal interpretation. Using Microsoft Excel and Google Sheets, the mean rating of respondents is calculated and averaged to get the overall rating, specific descriptive ratings are offered along with appropriate verbal interpretation.

In table 2.3, Item number 1, which states, "I believe that clean comfort rooms contribute positively to my physical health and well-being at school," obtained the highest

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mean score of 3.53, with a descriptive rating of "Strongly Agree" and a verbal interpretation of "Completely agrees with the statement."

Item number 3, which states, "I feel less stressed during school hours when I know the comfort rooms are clean," obtained the lowest mean score of 3.29, with a descriptive rating of "Strongly Agree" and a verbal interpretation of "Completely agrees with the statement."

The mean responses on comfort room cleanliness impact on student health and well-being is 3.46, which has a "Strongly Agree" descriptive rating and a verbal interpretation of "Completely agrees with the statement." This indicates that respondents fully acknowledge the role of clean comfort rooms in maintaining their health and overall well-being. Wang et al. (2021) emphasize that maintaining clean school facilities, including comfort rooms, significantly reduces student stress and uneasiness, ultimately supporting better academic engagement. Similarly, Shao (2020) highlights that cleanliness influences not only user satisfaction but also emotional well-being, which in turn affects students' academic attitudes. School of Scholars (2023) further supports this by stating that a clean school environment improves student health, focus, and performance, as hygiene maintenance prevents the spread of germs and reduces absenteeism. In line with this, Shaughnessy et al. (2022) argue that clean comfort rooms help prevent infectious diseases, thereby ensuring students remain present and actively engaged in their academic activities.

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Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

These findings reinforce that maintaining restroom hygiene is essential in fostering a healthier, more focused, and more productive student body.

The results indicate that students strongly recognize the importance of clean comfort rooms in maintaining their physical health and overall well-being. The high agreement level suggests that cleanliness in school restrooms contributes to a healthier environment, reducing stress and promoting better focus. When students have access to hygienic facilities, they feel more comfortable and secure, allowing them to engage more effectively in their academic activities. Although all responses reflect strong agreement, the slightly lower score for stress reduction implies that while cleanliness is valued, other factors may also influence students' stress levels during school hours. This highlights the need for a holistic approach that includes not only hygiene maintenance but also other supportive measures to enhance student well-being. Schools should continue prioritizing restroom cleanliness as part of a broader effort to foster a healthier, more focused, and productive learning environment.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Problem Number 3: Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of comfort room cleanliness and overall student academic engagement?

Table 3: Significant Relationship of Comfort Room Cleanliness and Overall Academic Engagement using Pearson r.

Variables	Mean	Descriptive Rating	r	p-value	Decision
Comfort Room Cleanliness (PLC) Mean	2.38	Disagree			
Academic Engagement (ISC-IFC-IHW) Mean	3.32	Strongly Agree	0.033	0.57	Accept the Null Hypothesis

****df 305**

This table shows the significant relationship between Comfort Room Cleanliness and Overall Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students using Pearson r Moment of Correlation. The table shows the composite mean for comfort room cleanliness and overall academic engagement, along with its corresponding description, mean rating of students, and Pearson r results.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

A Pearson Correlation Coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between comfort room cleanliness and academic engagement. The analysis revealed no significant relationship between the two variables, $r(305) = 0.033$, $p = 0.57$. This indicates that the cleanliness of comfort rooms does not directly influence students' academic engagement based on the data gathered.

However, prior studies contradict these findings and suggest that restroom cleanliness can impact students' engagement and learning experiences.

Abney et al. (2020) explored the relationship between cleanliness and student satisfaction in higher education institutions. Their study found a direct positive correlation between clean restroom conditions and overall student satisfaction, emphasizing that comfort room cleanliness significantly shapes students' perceptions of their learning environment.

Likewise, Dagoc (2020) examined student satisfaction with restroom facilities at Saint Michael College of Caraga and identified cleanliness, fragrance, and space availability as crucial factors affecting satisfaction. While many students were satisfied with the restrooms, cleanliness remained a significant concern. The study concluded that restroom conditions shape students' experiences, highlighting the need for effective monitoring systems and proper restroom management to ensure a cleaner and more conducive school atmosphere. These previous findings challenge the results of the present study by suggesting that comfort room cleanliness does impact students' overall academic engagement. The difference in findings may be attributed to variations in institutional policies, environmental factors, or student perceptions. Future research may

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

be needed to explore the role of hygiene, facility management, and infrastructure maintenance in influencing students' academic experiences.

Chapter V

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations offered.

Summary of Findings

From the analysis of the data collected and results obtained, the following significant findings are summarized.

1. Students Perceived Level of Comfort Room Cleanliness

The findings indicate that students generally perceive the comfort rooms as unclean. They reported issues such as the lack of hygiene products, unpleasant odors, and inconsistent maintenance. Many students expressed dissatisfaction with the overall cleanliness of the facilities. However, they also noted that vandalism in the restrooms is minimal and not a major concern.

2. Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on Academic Engagement

2.1 Student Satisfaction and Comfort

The findings show that students strongly believe clean restrooms contribute to their comfort and satisfaction in school. Many students see well-maintained comfort rooms as a sign that the school cares about their well-being. While they acknowledge the positive impact of cleanliness on their overall school experience, some feel that further improvements are needed to enhance restroom conditions.

2.2 Student Focus and Concentration

The findings suggest that students generally agree that comfort room cleanliness affects their ability to concentrate in school. They feel more comfortable using the comfort rooms when they are clean, which helps them stay focus during school hours. However, while cleanliness is seen as beneficial, some students believe it has only a minor impact on their concentration in lessons.

2.3 Student Health and Well-Being

The finding indicate that students strongly believe comfort room cleanliness is important for their health and well-being. They recognize that clean comfort rooms help maintain good hygiene and prevent health issues. Many students feel that having well-maintained facilities contributes to their overall comfort and sense of security at school. Additionally, cleanliness helps to prevent the spread of diseases, reduce stress, creating a more positive learning environment.

3. Relationship Between Comfort Room Cleanliness and Academic Engagement

The findings suggest that while comfort room cleanliness contributes to students' well-being, it does not have a direct impact on their overall academic engagement. Although students recognize the importance of hygiene and comfort, other factors may play a significant role in their academic engagement.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from the results of the study

1. Perceived Level of Comfort Room Cleanliness:

- Senior high school students perceive the comfort rooms in their school as generally unclean, with concerns about maintenance, availability of hygiene materials, and overall sanitation. Although students notice minimal vandalism, the lack of hygiene products and unpleasant odors remain significant issues.

2. Relationship Between Cleanliness and Academic Engagement Aspects:

- Students strongly believe that maintaining cleanliness in comfort rooms positively impacts their comfort and well-being. Clean restrooms reduce discomfort and distractions, which helps improve concentration in class. Proper hygiene also helps prevent illnesses and reduces stress caused by unclean conditions, contributing to students' overall health.

3. Significant Relationship Between Cleanliness and Overall Academic Engagement:

- The study found no significant direct relationship between comfort room cleanliness and overall academic engagement. Although students recognize the importance of hygiene and comfort, it appears that other factors may play a more substantial role in influencing academic performance.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Students are encouraged to practice self-discipline when using the comfort rooms by following proper hygiene and etiquette to help maintain cleanliness.
2. It is suggested that student organizations promote awareness campaigns about the importance of hygiene to foster a sense of responsibility among their peers.
3. The school administration may consider establishing clear policies regarding comfort room cleanliness, outlining proper usage and behavioral expectations while setting guidelines for non-compliance.
4. Conducting regular inspections and assigning designated staff to oversee cleanliness could help ensure proper maintenance of the comfort rooms.
5. Providing school personnel with adequate cleaning materials and proper training on sanitation practices may further enhance hygiene standards.
6. Ensuring a steady supply of essential hygiene products such as soap, toilet paper, and hand sanitizers is recommended to support students' well-being.
7. Implementing a feedback system where students can report cleanliness issues may help maintain better sanitation in the comfort rooms.
8. Integrating discussions on hygiene into subjects such as health, social studies, or homeroom guidance is recommended to emphasize its connection to student well-being and learning.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

9. Encouraging student participation in school cleanliness programs, such as sanitation efforts or comfort room maintenance initiatives, may help promote awareness and a sense of responsibility.
10. Implementing a scheduled cleaning routine is suggested to ensure that comfort rooms remain properly maintained and do not become a source of distraction or discomfort for students.
11. Collaboration between school administrators and student councils or organizations is encouraged to implement regular hygiene monitoring activities that promote accountability among students.
12. The local government may explore opportunities to support the school by providing resources for comfort room maintenance, including sanitation materials and funding for regular upkeep.
13. Partnering with LGUs to implement hygiene programs, awareness campaigns, or sanitation initiatives could further promote cleanliness and health among students.
14. Further research on the relationship between comfort room cleanliness and academic engagement is encouraged, considering additional factors that may influence student performance.
15. The use of qualitative or mixed-methods approaches in future studies is suggested to provide deeper insights into students' experiences and perceptions regarding school hygiene and learning environments.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

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Las Piñas City National Senior High School
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APPENDICES

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Appendix A

REQUEST LETTER FOR VALIDATION OF RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

January 31, 2025

Ms. Sylvia L. Lasala

Las Piñas National Senior High School-Doña Josefa Campus

Greetings!

We, the Group 3 of Grade GAS 12- Mindful will be conducting research entitled "**The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students**" as a course requirement in INQUIRIES, INVESTIGATION, AND IMMERSION.

With your expertise, we are humbly asking your permission to validate the research instrument of our research paper. We will submit to you the copy of our research paper once it is complete for your comments and approval.

We are looking forward that our request would merit your positive response. Thank you for your time and consideration!

Respectfully yours

Relente, Randel P.

One of the Researchers

Noted By:

(Sgd)

Sir Jovellano Ontog

Research Adviser

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School
Doña Josefa Campus

January 31, 2025

Mr. Regin Adrian Suba

Las Piñas National Senior High School-Doña Josefa Campus

Greetings!

We, the Group 3 of Grade GAS 12- Mindful will be conducting research entitled "**The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students**" as a course requirement in INQUIRIES, INVESTIGATION, AND IMMERSION.

With your expertise, we are humbly asking your permission to validate the research instrument of our research paper. We will submit to you the copy of our research paper once it is complete for your comments and approval.

We are looking forward that our request would merit your positive response. Thank you for your time and consideration!

Respectfully yours,

Relente, Randel P.

One of the Researchers

Noted By:

(Sgd)

Sir Jovellano Ontog

Research Adviser

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

January 31, 2025

Ms. Sheila Mae Nabora

Las Piñas National Senior High School-Doña Josefa Campus

Greetings!

We, the Group 3 of Grade GAS 12- Mindful will be conducting research entitled "**The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students**" as a course requirement in INQUIRIES, INVESTIGATION, AND IMMERSION.

With your expertise, we are humbly asking your permission to validate the research instrument of our research paper. We will submit to you the copy of our research paper once it is complete for your comments and approval.

We are looking forward that our request would merit your positive response. Thank you for your time and consideration!

Respectfully yours,

Relente, Randel P.

One of the Researchers

Noted By:

(Sgd)

Sir Jovellano Ontog

Research Adviser

General Academic Strand

Appendix B

DECLARATION OF ANTI - PLAGIARISM

1. We, Relente, Randel P., Camila, Amiel Kirby G., Quines, Shella Joy S., Pisit, Yanli Jade S., Estuita, Sharen S., Perez, Princess Ann T., and Latorre, Jovan B. understand that plagiarism is the act of taking and using another's ideas and works and passing them off as one's own. This includes explicitly copying the whole works of another person and/or using some parts of their work without proper acknowledgment and referencing.
2. We hereby attest to the originality of this research proposal and has cited properly all the references used. I further commit that all deliverables and the final research study emanating from this proposal shall be of original content. I shall use appropriate citations in referencing other works from various sources.
3. We understand that violation from this declaration and commitment shall be subjected to consequences and shall be dealt with accordingly by the Department of Education and (insert grant mechanism).

PROPONENT: **RELENTE, RANDEL P.**

PROPONENT: **CAMILA, AMIEL KIRBY G.**

PROPONENT: **QUINES, SHELLA JOY S.**

PROPONENT: **PISIT, YANLI JADE S.**

PROPONENT: **ESTUITA, SHAREN S.**

PROPONENT: **PEREZ, PRINCESS ANN T.**

PROPONENT: **LATORRE, JOVAN B.**

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Plagiarism Detector.net Jan 13, 2021

Plagiarism Scan Report

0% Plagiarized	100% Unique	Characters:169	Words:23
		Sentences:1	Speak Time: 1 Min

Excluded URL: None

Content Checked for Plagiarism

Research by Unilever (2021) states that poor comfort room conditions often discourage students from using them, leading to discomfort, distraction, and even absenteeism.

Plagiarism Scan Report

0% Plagiarized	100% Unique	Characters:426	Words:61
		Sentences:3	Speak Time: 1 Min

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In the Philippines, many public schools experience similar challenges. According to the Department of Education (DepEd), a significant number of schools lack access to clean water and functioning toilets, with Metro Manila being a prime example. Reports from Inquirer.net (2016) and GMA News (2014) highlight how non-functional and unsanitary comfort rooms cause discomfort and affect students ability to concentrate in class.

Plagiarism Scan Report

0% Plagiarized	100% Unique	Characters:484	Words:69
		Sentences:3	Speak Time: 1 Min

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

In Southeast Asia, the issue is particularly more common, with over 30% of schools lacking proper facilities (Eco-Business, 2018). Problems like water shortages, lack of privacy, and inadequate maintenance force students to avoid restrooms, negatively impacting their focus and performance. For girls, the situation is even more worse. During menstruation, many skip school due to the lack of proper hygiene facilities, disrupting their education and limiting future opportunities.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:854

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None

Content Checked for Plagiarism

Research further supports these observations. Sangalang et al. (2022) emphasize that unflushed waste, bad smells, and the absence of essential cleaning materials such as soap or sanitizers lead to dirty conditions and health risks. Poor maintenance contributes to stress, distraction, and absenteeism. Neglected restrooms also lower morale, as littering and vandalism exacerbate the problem, making the school atmosphere less conducive to learning (Kleopapple, 2019). On the other hand, clean and well-maintained restrooms significantly improve student satisfaction, health, and focus. Palar et al. (2022) highlight that better restroom management enhances hygiene and fosters a more positive school environment. Clean restrooms reduce illnesses, boost confidence, and create a setting where students can concentrate on their studies without distractions.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943). Maslow's theory emphasizes that people must have their basic physiological and safety needs met before they can focus on higher-level cognitive tasks such as learning. Clean comfort rooms address essential needs for hygiene and sanitation, empowering students to feel secure and comfortable in their learning environment. In terms of application of this theory in the study, When comfort rooms are clean and functional, students' physiological and safety needs are fulfilled. This promotes a healthy, positive, and conducive learning environment by eliminating distractions caused by discomfort or health concerns.

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Jan 12, 2025

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:304

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Reyes et al. (2024) highlight that the cleanliness of school facilities, including comfort rooms, contributes to student satisfaction, which in turn, positively impacts academic achievement. Their findings propose that a clean and well-maintained learning environment fosters better student performance.

Jan 12, 2025

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Aamir (2024) emphasize that clean restrooms reduce uneasiness and promote hygiene, creating a healthier and more conducive learning environment. These factors, according to the study, support students' academic success by reducing distractions and promoting better physical and mental wellbeing.

Jan 12, 2025

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Kabir et al. (2021) present a negative view, showing how insufficient cleanliness in school facilities, especially restrooms, negatively impacts students' satisfaction, academic performance, and overall well-being. The study calls attention to the need for regular cleaning and proper sanitation to maintain a conducive learning environment.

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Jan 12, 2025

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Dujosef et al. (2022) further emphasize this need, stating that clean restrooms are essential for students' wellbeing which significant resources must be allocated to cleanliness activities in schools.

Jan 12, 2025

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Abney et al. (2020) explore the relationship between cleanliness and student satisfaction in higher education institutions. They found that a direct positive correlation exists between clean restrooms and overall student satisfaction, suggesting that the state of school facilities especially in comfort rooms plays a significant role in forming students' perceptions of their learning environment.

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Sentences:2

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Plagiarism Scan Report

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Uleanya et al. (2021) examine the impact of clean restrooms on student health and well-being, emphasizing that maintaining hygienic conditions reduces absenteeism and supports academic performance. Their study advocates for regular cleaning schedules and the involvement of students in maintaining cleanliness to ensure a safe and healthy learning environment.

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Words:80

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Vanguard (2024) emphasizes the critical role of school cleanliness in improving student performance by creating a healthy, focused, and productive learning environment. The study highlights that clean facilities significantly reduce absenteeism by mitigating health risks associated with poor hygiene. Additionally, factors such as proper ventilation, temperature control, and accessible hygiene practices are identified as essential for fostering a conducive academic atmosphere. Cleanliness not only promotes physical health but also enhances cognitive engagement, affirming its positive impact on overall student outcomes.

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Courtenor et al. (2020) also support the positive connection between cleanliness and student satisfaction, emphasizing that students' perceptions of cleanliness are directly affected by the physical state of comfort rooms. Their study shows that clean restrooms contribute to a feeling of safety and well-being, which in turn improves students' overall satisfaction with their school environment.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Wang et al. (2021) explore the broader impacts of facility cleanliness on students' mental health, as the study concludes that maintaining clean school facilities, including comfort rooms, plays an important role in reducing stress and uneasiness among students, thus positively impacting their academic engagement.

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Winstet (2023) highlights the critical link between restroom sanitation and student health and engagement. The study reveals that unsanitary school restrooms can lead to the spread of illness, increased absenteeism, and decreased focus among students, all of which negatively impact their overall well-being and academic success. Poor restroom conditions often discourage students from utilizing the facilities, leading to discomfort and distraction during classes. This underscores the importance of maintaining clean and well-developed restrooms to support student health, foster engagement, and create an environment conducive to learning.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Vos and Gatzika (2023) offer a different perspective, challenging the commonly held belief that cleanliness directly impacts student learning. Their study suggests that students' perceptions of cleanliness are often shaped more by emotional and social factors than by the actual condition of the facilities. They argue that while cleanliness may impact student behavior, the emotional responses and social dynamics surrounding the learning environment may play an even more significant role. According to their research, improvements in cleanliness alone are insufficient unless accompanied by broader contextual changes, such as addressing social dynamics and environmental cues.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Sharma et al. (2024) emphasize that the quality of WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) facilities, including the cleanliness of school restrooms, significantly affects students' health, attendance, and academic performance. Poor sanitation, especially the absence of proper facilities for menstruating girls, leads to higher absenteeism and reduced focus in class. The study concludes that improving comfort room cleanliness and overall hygiene in schools is essential to enhancing students' learning experience and overall educational achievement.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Sungu (2023) conducted a study at Sta. Cruz Elementary School in Antipolo to evaluate the implementation of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) program and its relationship with the hygiene and sanitation practices of intermediate pupils. Using a descriptive correlational research design, the study included 85 teachers and 162 pupils from Grades IV to VI. The findings revealed a high level of WASH program implementation, particularly on promoting disease prevention and community health, as perceived by both teachers and pupils. Notably, the study identified a significant relationship between the program's implementation and the pupils' hygiene practices. By fostering proper hygiene habits, the WASH program not only contributes to improved health outcomes but also positively influences students' learning experiences. Healthier pupils are better equipped to engage in academic activities, demonstrating enhanced focus, reduced absenteeism, and greater overall academic performance. The study concludes that further improvements in WASH program management can create a more conducive environment for learning by addressing both health and hygiene needs.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Shaughnessy et al. (2022) also point to the need for cleanliness in student health and attendance. The author of this study argue that clean comfort rooms prevent the outbreak of infectious diseases, thus eliminating student absences and encouraging students to participate actively in school affairs. Clean facilities are therefore fundamental to ensuring students stay healthy and engaged in their studies. This study indicates that hygiene has a direct impact on attendance, as students are less likely to miss school due to health concerns emerging from poor hygiene practices.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Shao (2020) emphasizes how cleanliness can establish a positive setting for learning. Their study, focusing on public facilities, reflects that cleanliness matters are not only influential in user satisfaction but also in his emotional state; this emotional state further influences student attitudes toward his educational activities.

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Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:577

Words:77

Sentences:3

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Istichomah and Astuti (2023) emphasize the importance of maintaining proper sanitation facilities and ensuring regular cleaning of school facilities, such as comfort rooms, to promote student well-being and create a conducive learning environment. The authors argue that a clean environment supports students physical and mental wellbeing, improving their focus and engagement in academic activities. Furthermore, the study underscores that proper cleaning practices and a systematic approach to restroom maintenance can improve both student satisfaction and academic outcomes.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Words:155

Sentences:6

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Dagoc (2020) conducted a study to evaluate the level of student satisfaction with restroom facilities at Saint Michael College of Caraga. The research utilized a descriptive design and survey method to identify critical factors influencing restroom satisfaction, specifically cleanliness, fragrance, and overall space. The findings showed that even though most students expressed satisfaction with the current state of the restrooms, Cleanliness was the main issue identified by those students, besides complaints about bad fragrance and inadequate space. The study emphasized that restroom conditions play an important role in shaping students' experiences within the school environment. To address these issues and improve overall satisfaction, Dagoc suggested implementing proper monitoring systems and prioritizing improvements in restroom management. These enhancements aim to promote a cleaner, more comfortable, and student-friendly atmosphere, ultimately contributing to a better educational environment.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Sentences:4

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Gadeer et al. (2024) highlighted the importance of well-maintained school facilities in impacting students learning experiences and academic outcomes. The authors found a very strong positive relationship between the quality of school facilities, such as classrooms and comfort rooms, and student satisfaction. Satisfaction, along with supportive comfort room environments characterized by security and mutual respect, enhances academic performance. The conclusion of the research recommends investment in school infrastructures to promote an pleasant environment conducive to learning while presenting the holistic effects that cleanliness and facility maintenance have on student well-being and success.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Sharma et al. (2024) emphasize that the quality of WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) facilities, including the cleanliness of school restrooms, significantly affects students' health, attendance, and academic performance. Poor sanitation, especially the absence of proper facilities for menstruating girls, leads to higher absenteeism and reduced focus in class. The study concludes that improving comfort room cleanliness and overall hygiene in schools is essential to enhancing students' learning experience and overall educational achievement.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Palar et al. (2022) indicate that inadequate sanitation management in public institutions, such as government schools, results in poor hygiene and cleanliness, which can negatively affect user satisfaction and health. The absence of proper sanitation facilities and dedicated management for cleanliness in these settings points to the need for improvement. In contrast, the present study aims to explore how maintaining cleanliness in school comfort rooms positively influences student learning experiences, thus highlighting the gap in addressing sanitation issues and its broader implications on educational settings.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Baafi (2020) emphasized the critical role of the school physical environment in shaping academic performance among senior high school students. The study showed that students who were in schools with a well-maintained and conducive learning environment always performed better academically than those who were in less favorable conditions. Adequate school facilities, clean and functional spaces, were cited as key contributors to fostering a positive educational climate and improving student learning. This study supports the notion that cleanliness and maintenance of school facilities, including comfort rooms, are essential in creating an environment that fosters academic success and overall student well-being. This therefore aligns with the importance of comfort room cleanliness, suggesting that well-maintained facilities contribute to a conducive learning experience for students.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:1562

Words:215

Sentences:9

Speak Time:
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According to the School of Scholars (2023), a clean school environment essentially improves student health, focus, and academic performance. Clean restrooms reduce the spread of germs, in this manner minimizing illnesses and absenteeism, which ensures that students can participate fully in their academic activities. Furthermore, a clean and organized space promotes a sense of calm and safety, reduces anxiety, and enhances students' ability to concentrate on their studies. Proper cleaning also promotes good indoor air quality, hence supporting students respiratory health, which improves students' abilities to perform to the best of their capacities in school. Keeping school facilities, especially comfort rooms and public areas clean impacts the student's physical and mental well-being and in this way contributes to better focus and engagement. Besides the short-term gains, cleanliness in schools creates a long-term culture of personal cleanliness and environmental stewardship. Through incorporating sanitation practices and maintainability activities such as hand-washing campaigns, recycling programs, and effective waste management systems, schools instill values that extend beyond the confines of the comfort rooms. In conclusion, cleaning up school facilities is not just cleanliness but an important factor in making a safe, healthy, and supportive environment in learning. Efforts that keep the schools clean improve student involvement, wellness, and achievement while developing behavior that promotes long-term personal and social growth.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:622

Words:88

Sentences:3

Speak Time:
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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Magpusao et al. (2020) established that the availability of cleaning materials and the support of student cooperation in maintaining cleanliness are effective strategies for improving the overall cleanliness of school restrooms. The study conducted on Grade 12 students at Bestlink College demonstrates how providing students with the necessary tools to maintain cleanliness can help make a more secure and more comfortable school environment. Students dynamic support in maintaining cleanliness develops a sense of responsibility and cooperation, which in turn can lead to more positive engagement in learning activities.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:374

Words:58

Sentences:3

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None

Content Checked for Plagiarism

Doubtek (2021) supports this view by stating the role of student behavior in terms of comfort room cleanliness. The author stated that if the schools can encourage responsible behaviors, such as proper waste disposal and regular cleaning, they can minimize vandalism and other undesirable behaviors. This contributes to a more positive and conducive learning environment.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:584	Words:89
Sentences:4	Speak Time: 1 Min

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Shaughnessy et al. (2022) also point to the need for cleanliness in student health and attendance. The author of this study argue that clean comfort rooms prevent the outbreak of infectious diseases, thus eliminating student absences and encouraging students to participate actively in school affairs. Clean facilities are therefore fundamental to ensuring students stay healthy and engaged in their studies. This study indicates that hygiene has a direct impact on attendance, as students are less likely to miss school due to health concerns emerging from poor hygiene practices.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:642	Words:87
Sentences:4	Speak Time: 1 Min

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Yonash (2020) highlights the critical link between restroom sanitation and student health and engagement. The study reveals that unsanitary school restrooms can lead to the spread of illness, increased absenteeism, and diminished focus among students, all of which negatively impact their overall well-being and academic success. Poor restroom conditions often discourage students from utilizing the facilities, leading to discomfort and distraction during classes. This underscores the importance of maintaining clean and well-equipped restrooms to support student health, foster engagement, and create an environment conducive to learning.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:664	Words:118
Sentences:5	Speak Time: 1 Min

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Thao et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of maintaining hygienic restrooms in schools through innovative methods, such as integrating Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) predictive models. These systems collect real-time data on ammonia (NH₃) concentrations and relative humidity (RH), enabling timely cleaning interventions and ensuring hygienic conditions. Unhygienic restrooms are often linked to health issues, such as the spread of infections, which can result in increased absenteeism and reduced academic performance. By addressing restroom conditions proactively, schools can create a safer and more conducive environment for learning. The study by Le Quang et al. highlights how advanced monitoring systems can effectively mitigate these risks, ensuring student well-being and enhancing the overall learning experience.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Sentences:3	Speak Time: 1 Min

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Cha et al. (2020) also conduct studies on the school sanitation and overall engagement of students. The author of the study stated that well-maintained restrooms contribute to a positive learning environment by reducing stressors that can detract from students focus on academic tasks. This study suggests that the cleanliness of school facilities directly correlates with students ability to concentrate and perform better in their studies.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:681	Words:95
Sentences:4	Speak Time: 1 Min

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Content Checked for Plagiarism

Vos and Galetzka (2020) offer a different perspective, challenging the commonly held belief that cleanliness directly impacts student learning. Their study suggests that students perceptions of cleanliness are often shaped more by emotional and social factors than by the actual condition of the facilities. They argue that while cleanliness may impact student behavior, the emotional responses and social dynamics surrounding the learning environment may play an even more significant role. According to their research, improvements in cleanliness alone are insufficient unless accompanied by broader contextual changes, such as addressing social dynamics and environmental cues.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:642	Words:86
Sentences:4	Speak Time: 1 Min

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Estacio and Gopez (2021) address concerns regarding the cleanliness of comfort rooms in schools, particularly at Bulacan State University. Their study focuses on cleaning methods and communication systems but does not fully investigate how restroom cleanliness impacts students learning experiences beyond just satisfaction. They emphasize the importance of improving cleaning procedures and communication channels to ensure proper cleanliness. However, their study overlooks broader factors such as the overall facility design, hygiene education, and regulatory support, which are key to making lasting improvements in the school environment.

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Doña Josefa Campus

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:168

Words:163

Sentences:7

Speak Time:
2 Min

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None

Content Checked for Plagiarism

Sunga (2023) conducted a study at Sta. Cruz Elementary School in Antipolo to evaluate the implementation of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) program and its relationship with the hygiene and sanitation practices of intermediate pupils. Using a descriptive correlational research design, the study included 85 teachers and 362 pupils from Grades (IV to V). The findings revealed a high level of WASH program implementation, particularly in promoting disease prevention and community health, as perceived by both teachers and pupils. Notably, the study identified a significant relationship between the program's implementation and the pupils' hygiene practices. By fostering proper hygiene habits, the WASH program not only contributes to improved health outcomes but also positively influences students' learning experiences. Healthier pupils are better equipped to engage in academic activities, demonstrating enhanced focus, reduced absenteeism, and greater overall academic performance. The study concludes that further improvements in WASH program management can create a more conducive environment for learning by addressing both health and hygiene needs.

Jan 12, 2025

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:640

Words:94

Sentences:3

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while Azmi et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of cleanliness in public restrooms for users' comfort and well-being, their study primarily focuses on commercial spaces rather than educational settings. The findings of their study, while relevant to common cleanliness practices, do not directly translate to the school environment, where the focus is on improving student learning rather than client satisfaction in public spaces. This presents a limitation in applying their results to the educational context, which requires a focus on factors such as student engagement, academic performance, and the affect of cleanliness on learning.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Characters:526

Words:94

Sentences:3

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Madeira et al. (2020) broaden the discussion by recommending that cleanliness should be viewed in conjunction with other factors such as leadership support and authoritative practices. Their study demonstrates that while cleanliness is a critical factor, it should be part of a all-encompassing approach to improving school environments. They emphasize that leadership and staff involvement in maintaining cleanliness, alongside regular cleaning schedules, are key to making a supportive and effective learning environment.

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Plagiarism Scan Report

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Okoro et al. (2020) highlight how essential water is in keeping school restrooms clean and functional. Their study found that while most restrooms were well-maintained, a temporary lack of water led to a noticeable decline in hygiene. This shows that without a steady water supply, maintaining proper sanitation becomes a challenge, creating an uncomfortable and unhealthy environment for students. Poor restroom conditions can be distracting and even harmful to student well-being, making it harder to focus on learning. The study reinforces the need for consistent water access and proper facility management to ensure restrooms remain clean, safe, and supportive of a positive educational experience.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Thompson S. (2023) emphasizes that maintaining clean and well-equipped school washrooms is essential for fostering a positive learning environment. Proper hygiene facilities help reduce the spread of illnesses, enhance student comfort, and support emotional well-being, all of which contribute to students' ability to focus and participate in academic activities. Additionally, well-maintained restrooms promote privacy, dignity, and inclusivity by ensuring accessibility for all students, creating a supportive atmosphere that encourages academic engagement. Schools that prioritize restroom cleanliness demonstrate a commitment to student welfare, positively influencing school culture, reputation, and overall student experience. Furthermore, integrating hygiene education within restroom spaces reinforces proper sanitation habits among students. These insights align with the broader understanding that cleanliness in educational environments directly impacts student satisfaction, health, and academic engagement, highlighting the necessity of high sanitation standards in schools.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Adewusi and Oguntokun (2024) highlight the critical role of accessible and well-maintained comfort rooms in fostering a healthy and conducive learning environment. Their study reveals that the poor state of sanitary facilities in a major academic institution in South West Nigeria negatively impacts student well-being, hygiene, and overall school experience. With a student-to-toilet ratio of 1:195—far exceeding recommended standards—students face significant challenges in accessing clean and functional restrooms. The study further identifies key factors influencing restroom utilization, including proper lighting, ventilation, water supply, privacy, security, accessibility for disabled individuals, and clear signage. Many restrooms remain locked or inadequately maintained, leading to unhygienic practices such as open defecation, which poses serious health risks. These findings emphasize the urgent need for institutions to prioritize restroom accessibility, regular maintenance, and proper sanitation measures to support student health, comfort, and academic engagement. Ensuring the availability of clean and accessible comfort rooms not only improves hygiene but also contributes to a more positive and productive educational environment.

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Maba (2022) emphasizes that maintaining a healthy school environment is essential for fostering a conducive learning atmosphere. The study found that to ensure school health, essential health standards must be carefully and intensively implemented. By prioritizing sanitation and hygiene, schools can create an environment where students can study well and comfortably. A well-maintained educational setting enhances student focus, reduces health risks, and supports academic engagement, reinforcing the importance of cleanliness and proper facility management in schools.

Mar 19, 2025

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Words:81

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Fletcher B. Dressler's School Hygiene Theory highlights the importance of maintaining hygiene and sanitation within school environments to promote students' health and academic performance. According to Dressler, maintaining clean and hygienic facilities within schools helps reduce health risks, enhance students' comfort, and improve their ability to focus on learning. In the context of this study, the School Hygiene Theory supports the idea that clean comfort rooms contribute positively to students' physical and mental well-being, thereby fostering better academic engagement and satisfaction.

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Maslow's Chain of command of Needs (1943), Maslow's hypothesis emphasizes that people must have their essential physiological and security needs met some time recently they can center on higher-level cognitive assignments such as learning. Clean consolation rooms address basic needs for cleanliness and sanitation, engaging understudies to feel secure and comfortable in their learning environment. In terms of application of this hypothesis in the think about, When consolation rooms are clean and useful, students' physiological and security needs are satisfied. This advances a sound, positive, and conducive learning environment by killing diversions caused by distress or wellbeing concerns.

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Plagiarism Scan Report

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Casperson (2024) highlights the critical role of school restroom cleanliness in maintaining student health, satisfaction, and academic success. Unsanitary restrooms can negatively impact students' perceptions of their school, discourage restroom use, and increase the spread of germs, ultimately affecting their well-being and focus in class. A lack of clean and well-maintained facilities can lead to discomfort, distractions, and absenteeism, all of which hinder students' ability to fully engage in their academic tasks. To address these concerns, the implementation of touchless fixtures, such as sensor-operated faucets and flush valves, is recommended to minimize germ transmission. Additionally, restroom designs should allow users to exit without touching doors to further reduce bacterial spread. Proper maintenance, regular cleaning, and effective ventilation are essential in preventing unpleasant odors and maintaining hygiene standards. School restroom sanitation should be a top priority, as a well-maintained facility contributes to a positive school environment and supports students' overall success. A clean and hygienic school building enhances student satisfaction and fosters a conducive atmosphere for learning by promoting focus, comfort, and well-being. Students who have access to clean restrooms are less likely to experience stress or anxiety related to poor hygiene conditions, allowing them to concentrate better on their studies. Furthermore, improved restroom conditions provide a sense of security and dignity, making students feel more comfortable in their school environment. To achieve this, schools should adopt strict sanitation practices, including the use of disinfectants, installation of no-touch garbage bins, and continuous promotion of proper handwashing. Additionally, reinforcing school morale and student responsibility can discourage vandalism and help sustain restroom cleanliness. By prioritizing hygiene and maintenance, schools can create a healthier and more supportive educational setting that enhances student engagement, academic performance, and overall well-being.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Excluded URL: None

Content Checked for Plagiarism

The Descriptive - Correlational Research Design is supported by Best, M. R. & Kahn, J. V. (1972) in Research Education, which emphasizes that correlational studies can determine the degree of relationship between variables in educational settings, even though they do not confirm direct causation.

Plagiarism Scan Report

Excluded URL: None

Content Checked for Plagiarism

Canoco et al. (2024) emphasize the importance of maintaining comfortable and accessible restroom facilities in educational institutions and their impact on student academic engagement. Their study at Cebu Technological University-Pinamungajan Campus highlights how restroom cleanliness, privacy, hygiene standards, and accessibility contribute to a positive campus environment. Comfort plays a crucial role in restroom usability, ensuring that facilities are clean, well-maintained, and properly equipped. Accessibility further promotes inclusivity by ensuring restrooms accommodate diverse needs, including individuals with disabilities. By actively engaging with the campus community, the study identifies key challenges and areas for improvement, reinforcing the need for institutions to prioritize restroom maintenance and accessibility. Providing well-maintained facilities not only enhances student well-being but also supports academic engagement by reducing distractions, discomfort, and health-related absenteeism. A clean and accessible restroom environment enables students to focus better on their studies, fostering a more productive and supportive educational experience.

Appendix C

VALIDATED RESEARCH SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

1

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by the researchers of Group 3 from Grade 12 Mindful: General Academic Strand. We are requesting your cooperation to answer our questionnaires for our research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students". Your knowledge, concerns, and response are a sure help for us in achieving our goal. Rest assured that the data we will gather will remain absolutely confidential and to be used for academic purposes only. We are hoping that this request would merit your positive response. Again, thank you for accepting our concern. May God bless you.

I give my consent to researchers to gather my information for their research entitled The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School-Doña Josefa Campus. I am aware that the main purpose of this study is to find out how comfort room cleanliness affects the academic experiences of senior high school students. I also understand that my participation in this research is voluntary, and all information and answers from me will be treated confidentially and will only be used for this study. I understand that during the research study, at any time, I may withdraw from participation without any questions or loss of any privileges. Therefore, by consenting, I am agreeing to participate in this research study.

THE IMPACT OF COMFORT ROOM CLEANLINESS TO THE ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Good Day! We are the researchers from GAS 12-Mindful, currently studying The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School-Doña Josefa Campus. This study aims to determine the Impact of comfort room cleanliness on Academic Engagement of senior high school students. There are no significant risks associated with participating in this research. Your responses will be kept confidential and anonymous, and will only be used for this study. Thank you for your participation!

Name (optional): _____ Strand - Grade & Section _____

Direction: Read each statement and select the checkbox that best represents your level of agreement, with options ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

4 - Strongly Agree 3 - Agree 2 - Disagree 1 - Strongly Disagree

Section 1: Perceived Level of Cleanliness

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in DJC generally clean.				
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms on campus.				
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms in DJC meets acceptable hygiene standards.				
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.				
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.				
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.				
7. I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms.				
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.				
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.				
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.				

Section 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.				
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.				
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.				
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.				

5. I always prefer to use a clean restroom, even if a dirty one is easier to access.				
6. I feel respected as a student when I see that the comfort rooms are well-maintained.				
7. I believe that clean comfort rooms show the school's commitment to student well-being.				
8. I feel that my overall satisfaction with school facilities depends on the cleanliness of the comfort rooms.				
9. I believe that clean comfort rooms improve my overall school experience.				
10. I think that dirty restrooms negatively impact my perception of the school.				

Section 3: Impact on Student Focus and Concentration

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find it easier to focus in class when the comfort rooms are clean.				
2. I prefer using the comfort rooms when they are clean during school hours.				
3. I feel more focused on my studies after using a clean comfort room.				
4. I feel more at ease during class when the comfort rooms are clean.				
5. I feel more prepared to participate in class activities after using a clean restroom.				
6. I feel that clean comfort rooms help me concentrate better in lessons.				
7. I feel more engaged in class discussions after using a well-maintained restroom.				
8. I believe that the cleanliness of the comfort rooms positively affects my attentiveness during lectures.				
9. I find it easier to concentrate in school when I know the restrooms are well-maintained.				
10. I believe that regular cleaning of the comfort rooms helps me stay focused on my studies.				

Section 4: Impact on Student Health and Well-Being

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I believe that clean restrooms contribute positively to my physical health and well-being at school.				
2. I feel confident that the cleanliness of the restrooms helps prevent health issues for students.				
3. I feel less stressed during school hours when I know the comfort rooms are clean.				
4. I believe that clean restrooms promote good mental well-being.				
5. I feel that using a clean restroom helps me avoid illness or infections.				
6. I feel at ease knowing that the hygiene standards in the comfort rooms meet my needs.				
7. I believe that maintaining hygiene in restrooms is essential for promoting student health.				
8. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better overall health for students.				
9. I feel safer using a clean restroom compared to an unclean one.				
10. I feel motivated to maintain better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean.				

Appendix D

INFORMED CONSENT FOR RESPONDENTS

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by the researchers of Group 3 from Grade 12 Mindful, General Academic Strand. We are requesting your cooperation to answer our questionnaires for our research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students. Your knowledge, concerns, and response are a sure help for us in achieving our goal. Rest assured that the data we will gather will remain absolutely confidential and to be used for academic purposes only. We are hoping that this request would merit your positive response. Again, thank you for accepting our concern. May God bless you.

- I give my consent to researchers to gather my information for their research entitled The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus. I am aware that the main purpose of this study is to find out how comfort room cleanliness affects the academic experiences of senior high school students. I also understand that my participation in this research is voluntary, and all information and answers from me will be treated confidentially and will only be used for this study. I understand that during the research study, at any time, I may withdraw from participation without any questions or loss of any privileges. Therefore, by consenting. I am agreeing to participate in this research study

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Appendix E

APPROVED VALIDATION RUBRIC OF RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Department of Education
Department of Education
National Capital Region
SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF LAS PIÑAS CITY
LAS PIÑAS CITY NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - DOÑA JOSEFA CAMPUS
JOSEFA AVE., DOÑA JOSEFA VILLAGE, ALMANZA UNO, LAS PIÑAS CITY

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FORM

<i>Name of Researcher/s:</i> Camila, Arnel Kirby G. Perez, Princess Ann Quines, Shella Joy Rolente, Randel P. Pisil, Yanni Jade S. Estuita, Sharen S. Latorre, Jovan B.		<i>Year and Section:</i> 12-Mindful <i>Inquiries, Investigations and Immersion Teacher:</i> Jovetiano V. Ontog
<i>Title of Research:</i> The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness to the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students		

Scale	Interpretation	Description
5	Very High Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 0-5% error
4	High Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 6-10% error
3	Less Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 11-15% error
2	Less Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 16-20% error
1	Not Valid at All	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 21-25% error

Direction: This tool asks for your evaluation of the questionnaire to be used in the data gathering for the investigation stated above, to establish its validity. You are requested to give your honest assessment using the criteria stated below. Please check (✓) only one from the selection.

Indicators	Rating				
	5	4	3	2	1
The indicators in the questionnaire consistently and accurately measure each variables of the investigation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The questionnaire fits with the variable under investigation, thus measuring what it tends to measure.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The questionnaire has the capability to measure items of variable within a given time frame.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The questionnaire has the ability to distinguish the characteristics or the properties of differing attributes of the subjects under study.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The questionnaire has the ability to gather factual data, eliminating biases and subjectivity.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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	Quick and complete data can be generated by the questionnaire within the time frame allowed to obtain data.	/			
	The questionnaire has no influence on the variables being measured.	/			
	The questionnaire is capable of generating data that will be of value and practical use to sectors concerned in the investigation.	/			
Clarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are direct and specific. Only one question is asked at a time. The participants can understand what is being asked. There are no <i>double-barreled</i> questions (two questions in one). 	/			
Wordiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questions are concise. There are no unnecessary words 	/			
Negative Wording	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questions are asked using the affirmative (e.g., instead of asking, "Which methods are not used?", the researcher asks, "Which methods are used?") 	/			
Overlapping Responses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No response covers more than one choice. All possibilities are considered. There are no ambiguous questions. 	/			
Balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are unbiased and do not lead the participants to a response. The questions are asked using a neutral tone. 	/			
Use of Jargon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The terms used are understandable by the target population. There are no clichés or hyperbole in the wording of the questions. 	/			
Appropriateness of Responses Listed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The choices listed allow participants to respond appropriately. The responses apply to all situations or offer a way for those to respond with unique situations. 	/			
Use of Technical Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of technical language is minimal and appropriate. All acronyms are defined. 	/			
Application to Praxis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions asked relate to the daily practices or expertise of the potential participants. 	/			
Relationship to Problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are sufficient to resolve the problem in the study The questions are sufficient to answer the research questions. The questions are sufficient to obtain the purpose of the study. 	/			

Validated by: *Sylvia C. Lasala*

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JOSEFA AVE., DOÑA JOSEFA VILLAGE, ALMANZA UNO, LAS PIÑAS CITY

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FORM

Name of Researchers: Camila, Armiel Kirby G. Perez, Princess Ann Quimes, Shella Joy Rolente, Randel P. Pisit, Yanli Jade S. Estuita, Sharen S. Latorre, Jovan B.	Year and Section: 12-Mindful Inquiries, Investigations and Immersion Teacher: Jovellano V. Ortog
Title of Research: The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness to the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students	

Scale	Interpretation	Description
5	Very High Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 0-5% error
4	High Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 8-10% error
3	Less Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 11-15% error
2	Less Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 16-20% error
1	Not Valid at All	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 21-25% error

Direction: This tool asks for your evaluation of the questionnaire to be used in the data gathering for the investigation stated above, to establish it's validity. You are requested to give your honest assessment using the criteria stated below. Please check (✓) only one from the selection

Indicators	Rating				
	5	4	3	2	1
Identified Variables/Constructs in the Study	The indicators in the questionnaire consistently and accurately measure each variables of the investigation				
	The questionnaire fits with the variable under investigation, thus measuring what it tends to measure.				
	The questionnaire has the capability to measure items of variable within a given time frame.				
	The questionnaire has the ability to distinguish the characteristics or the properties of differing attributes of the subjects under study.				
	The questionnaire has the ability to gather factual data, eliminating biases and subjectivity.				

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	Quick and complete data can be generated by the questionnaire within the time frame allowed to obtain data.	✓			
	The questionnaire has no influence on the variables being measured.	✓			
	The questionnaire is capable of generating data that will be of value and practical use to sectors concerned in the investigation.		✓		
Clarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are direct and specific. Only one question is asked at a time. The participants can understand what is being asked. There are no double-barreled questions (two questions in one). 		✓		
Wordiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questions are concise. There are no unnecessary words 	✓			
Negative Wording	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questions are asked using the affirmative (e.g., instead of asking, "Which methods are not used?", the researcher asks, "Which methods are used?") 	✓			
Overlapping Responses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No response covers more than one choice. All possibilities are considered. There are no ambiguous questions. 		✓		
Balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are unbiased and do not lead the participants to a response. The questions are asked using a neutral tone. 	✓			
Use of Jargon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The terms used are understandable by the target population. There are no clichés or hyperbole in the wording of the questions. 		✓		
Appropriateness of Responses Listed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The choices listed allow participants to respond appropriately. The responses apply to all situations or offer a way for those to respond with unique situations. 	✓			
Use of Technical Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of technical language is minimal and appropriate. All acronyms are defined. 		✓		
Application to Praxis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions asked relate to the daily practices or expertise of the potential participants. 			✓	
Relationship to Problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are sufficient to resolve the problem in the study The questions are sufficient to answer the research questions. The questions are sufficient to obtain the purpose of the study. 			✓	

Validator

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RESEARCH INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FORM

Name of Researchers: Camila, Arniel Kirby G. Perez, Princess Ann Guines, Shella Joy Relento, Randel P. Pisk, Yanti Jade S. Estuta, Sharin S. Latorre, Jovan B.		Year and Section: 12-Mindful Inquiries, Investigations and Immersion Teacher: Jovellano V. Ontog
Title of Research: The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness to the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students		

Scale	Interpretation	Description
5	Very High Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 0-5% error
4	High Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 6-10% error
3	Less Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 11-15% error
2	Less Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 16-20% error
1	Not Valid at All	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 21-25% error

Direction: This tool asks for your evaluation of the questionnaire to be used in the data gathering for the investigation stated above, to establish it's validity. You are requested to give your honest assessment using the criteria stated below. Please check (/) only one from the selection

Indicators	Rating				
	5	4	3	2	1
Identified Variables/Constructs in the Study	The indicators in the questionnaire consistently and accurately measure each variables of the investigation	/			
	The questionnaire fits with the variable under investigation, thus measuring what it tends to measure.	/			
	The questionnaire has the capability to measure items of variable within a given time frame.	/			
	The questionnaire has the ability to distinguish the characteristics or the properties of differing attributes of the subjects under study.	/			
	The questionnaire has the ability to gather factual data, eliminating biases and subjectivity.	/			

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	Quick and complete data can be generated by the questionnaire within the time frame allowed to obtain data.		/			
	The questionnaire has no influence on the variables being measured.			/		
	The questionnaire is capable of generating data that will be of value and practical use to sectors concerned in the investigation.		/			
Clarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are direct and specific. Only one question is asked at a time. The participants can understand what is being asked. There are no double-barreled questions (two questions in one). 		/			
Wordiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questions are concise. There are no unnecessary words. 			/		
Negative Wording	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questions are asked using the affirmative (e.g., Instead of asking, "Which methods are not used?", the researcher asks, "Which methods are used?") 		/			
Overlapping Responses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No response covers more than one choice. All possibilities are considered. There are no ambiguous questions. 		/			
Balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are unbiased and do not lead the participants to a response. The questions are asked using a neutral tone. 	/				
Use of Jargon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The terms used are understandable by the target population. There are no clichés or hyperbole in the wording of the questions. 			/		
Appropriateness of Responses Listed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The choices listed allow participants to respond appropriately. The responses apply to all situations or offer a way for those to respond with unique situations. 		/			
Use of Technical Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of technical language is minimal and appropriate. All acronyms are defined. 		/			
Application to Praxis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions asked relate to the daily practices or expertise of the potential participants. 			/		
Relationship to Problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questions are sufficient to resolve the problem in the study. The questions are sufficient to answer the research questions. The questions are sufficient to obtain the purpose of the study. 		/			

1/21/21

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Appendix F

Copy of Answered Research Instrument

99

THE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (DepEd) DIVISION OFFICE - LAS PIÑAS CITY, in partnership with the Department of Education - Las Piñas City National Senior High School, conducted a research study on the impact of clean restrooms on student health and well-being. The study aims to determine the effect of clean restrooms on students' health, satisfaction, and academic performance. The results of this study will be used to improve the quality of the school environment and to provide better services to the students.

SECTION 1: Maintenance and Cleanliness

Questions

	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in LNSC generally clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms at LNSC.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms in LNSC meets acceptable hygiene standards.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. I rarely experience unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7. I observe proper waste or sanitation in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

SECTION 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions

	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

99

SECTION 3: Impact on Student Focus and Concentration

Questions

	4	3	2	1
1. I find it easier to focus in class when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. I prefer using the comfort rooms when they are clean during school hours.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I feel more focused on my studies after using a clean comfort room.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I feel more at ease during class when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5. I feel more prepared to participate in class activities after using a clean restroom.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. I feel that clean restrooms help me concentrate better in lessons.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7. I feel more engaged in class discussions after using a well-maintained restroom.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8. I believe that the cleanliness of the comfort rooms positively affects my attentiveness during lectures.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
9. I find it easier to concentrate in school when I know the restrooms are well-maintained.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
10. I believe that regular cleaning of the comfort rooms helps me stay focused on my studies.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

SECTION 4: Impact on Student Health and Well-Being

Questions

	4	3	2	1
1. I believe that clean restrooms contribute positively to my physical health and well-being at school.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. I feel confident that the cleanliness of the restrooms helps prevent health issues for students.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I feel less stressed during school hours when I know the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I believe that clean restrooms promote good mental well-being.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5. I feel that using a clean restroom helps me avoid illness or infections.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. I feel at ease knowing that the hygiene standards in the comfort rooms meet my needs.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7. I believe that maintaining hygiene in restrooms is essential for promoting student health.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better overall health for students.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
9. I feel safer using a clean restroom compared to an unclean one.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
10. I feel encouraged to maintain better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

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98

THE IMPACT OF COMFORT ROOM CLEANLINESS TO THE ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Name: _____ Grade & Section: **TVB-01 12.P.000-1**

Directions: Read each statement and select the checkbox that best represents your level of agreement with answers ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

4 - Strongly Agree 3 - Agree 2 - Disagree 1 - Strongly Disagree

Section 1: Perceived Level of Cleanliness

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in OJC generally clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms on campus.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms in OJC meets acceptable hygiene standards.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
7. I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		

Section 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		

98

5. I rarely prefer to use a clean restroom, even if it's long line to wait to go.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
6. I feel responsible as a student when I see that the comfort rooms are well-maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
7. I believe that clean comfort rooms show the school's commitment to student well-being.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
8. I feel that my overall satisfaction with school facilities depends on the cleanliness of the comfort rooms.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
9. I believe that clean comfort rooms improve my overall school experience.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
10. I think that dirty restrooms negatively impact my perception of the school.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		

Section 3: Impact on Student Focus and Concentration

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find it easier to focus in class when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
2. I prefer using the comfort rooms when they are clean during school hours.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I feel more focused on my studies after using a clean comfort room.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
4. I feel more at ease during class when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
5. I feel more prepared to participate in class activities after using a clean restroom.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
6. I feel that clean comfort rooms help me concentrate better in lessons.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
7. I feel more engaged in class discussions after using a well-maintained restroom.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
8. I believe that the cleanliness of the comfort rooms positively affects my attentiveness during lectures.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
9. I find it easier to concentrate in school when I know the restrooms are well-maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
10. I believe that regular cleaning of the comfort rooms helps me stay focused on my studies.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		

Section 4: Impact on Student Health and Well-Being

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I believe that clean restrooms contribute positively to my physical health and well-being at school.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
2. I feel confident that the cleanliness of the restrooms helps prevent health issues for students.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I feel less stressed during school hours when I know the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
4. I believe that clean restrooms promote good mental well-being.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
5. I feel that using a clean restroom helps me avoid illness or infections.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
6. I feel at ease knowing that the hygiene standards in the comfort rooms meet my needs.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
7. I believe that maintaining hygiene in restrooms is essential for promoting student health.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
8. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better overall health for students.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
9. I feel safer using a clean restroom compared to an unclean one.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
10. I feel motivated to maintain better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

89

You are being invited to participate in a research study sponsored by the researchers from the Department of Health's Office of Academic Community Outreach. We are requesting your cooperation to answer the questionnaire in our research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students". Your participation, comments, and responses are a valuable asset in achieving the goal. Please ensure that the data is well-protected, remains anonymous, confidential, and will not be available to anyone else. We are hoping that our research would assist your health concerns. Thank you for your assistance in this research. May God bless you!

II. I give my consent to participate in this research study because I am interested in the study. I understand that the researchers from the Department of Health's Office of Academic Community Outreach are conducting the study. I also understand that my participation in this research is voluntary and that I can withdraw my consent at any time. I will not be held responsible for any loss of data or for any other consequences that may arise during the study. I am willing to participate in this research study.

THE IMPACT OF COMFORT ROOM CLEANLINESS ON THE ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Good day! We are the researchers from OAC, TE and I am currently studying the impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus. The study aims to determine the impact of comfort room cleanliness on Academic Engagement of senior high school students. There are the significant data associated with participating in this research. Your responses will be kept confidential and anonymous, and will only be used for this study. Thank you for your participation!

Name (optional): _____ Grade - Class & Section: 10 - IV B UCT / Appendix

Direction: Read each statement and select the checkbox that best represents your level of agreement, with options ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

4 - Strongly Agree 3 - Agree 2 - Disagree 1 - Strongly Disagree

Section 1: Perceived Level of Cleanliness

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in OAC generally clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms on campus.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms in OAC meets appropriate hygiene standards.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7. I observe minimal traffic or vandalism in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Section 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

89

Section 3: Impact on Student Focus and Concentration

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find it easier to focus or read when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. I rarely get distracted when I am in a clean comfort room.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I feel more comfortable participating in class activities when I am in a clean comfort room.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I feel more motivated to participate in class activities when I am in a clean comfort room.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5. I feel more comfortable participating in class activities when I am in a clean comfort room.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. I believe that the cleanliness of the comfort rooms positively affects my concentration during lessons.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7. I find it easier to concentrate in class when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8. I believe that regular cleaning of the comfort rooms helps me stay focused on my studies.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Section 4: Impact on Student Health and Well-Being

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I believe that a clean restroom contributes positively to my physical health and well-being as a student.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. I feel confident that the cleanliness of the restrooms helps prevent health issues for students.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I feel less stressed during school days when I know the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I believe that clean restrooms promote good mental well-being.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5. I feel that using a clean restroom helps me feel stress-free in class.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. I feel at ease knowing that the hygiene standards in the comfort rooms meet my needs.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7. I believe that maintaining hygiene in restrooms is essential for promoting student health.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better overall health for students.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
9. I feel safer using a clean restroom compared to an unclean one.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
10. I feel motivated to maintain better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

193

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by the researchers of **Topic 7** from **Grade 12** **Strand: General Academic Strand**. We are requesting your cooperation in allowing our questionnaire to see how well students perceive and experience the cleanliness of the Academic Engagement of Senior High Schools facilities. Your thoughtful, honest, and complete answers will help us with defining our goals. We are confident that the data we will gather will become absolutely confidential and will be used for the intended purposes only. We are hoping that this research would make your academic experience better. Thank you for accepting our invitation. We'll send them soon.

I agree to participate in this research study.

THE IMPACT OF COMFORT ROOM CLEANLINESS TO THE ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Good Day! We are the researchers from **Grade 12** currently studying the impact of **Century Basin Cleanliness** in the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students at **Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus**. This study aims to determine the impact of **comfort room cleanliness** on students' engagement of senior high school students. There are no significant risks associated with participating in this research. Your responses will be kept confidential and anonymous, and will only be used for this study. Thank you for your participation!

Name (optional): Yolene Strand - Grade & Section: APM 12 - Redwood

Directions: Read each statement and select the checkbox that best represents your level of agreement, with options ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

4 - Strongly Agree 3 - Agree 2 - Disagree 1 - Strongly Disagree

Section 1: Perceived Level of Cleanliness

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in DAC generally clean.				
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms on campus.				
3. I believe that cleanliness of the comfort rooms in DAC meets acceptable hygiene standards.				
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.				
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.				
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.				
7. I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms.				
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.				
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.				
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.				

Section 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.				
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.				
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.				
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.				

193

5. I always prefer to use a clean restroom, even if it only takes a second to access.

6. I feel respected as a student when I see that the comfort rooms are well-maintained.

7. I believe that clean comfort rooms show the school's commitment to student well-being.

8. I feel that my overall satisfaction with school facilities depends on the cleanliness of the comfort rooms.

9. I believe that clean comfort rooms enhance my overall school experience.

10. I think that dirty restrooms negatively impact my perception of the school.

Section 3: Impact on Student Focus and Concentration

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find it easier to focus at class when the comfort rooms are clean.				
2. I prefer using the comfort rooms when they are clean during school hours.				
3. I feel more focused on my studies after using a clean comfort room.				
4. I feel more at ease during class when the comfort rooms are clean.				
5. I feel more prepared to participate in class activities after using a clean restroom.				
6. I feel that clean comfort rooms help me concentrate better in lessons.				
7. I feel more engaged in class discussions after using a well-maintained restroom.				
8. I believe that the cleanliness of the comfort rooms positively affects my attentiveness during lessons.				
9. I find it easier to concentrate in school when I know the restrooms are well-maintained.				
10. I believe that regular cleaning of the comfort rooms helps me stay focused on my studies.				

Section 4: Impact on Student Health and Well-Being

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I believe that clean restrooms contribute positively to my physical health and well-being at school.				
2. I feel confident that the cleanliness of the restrooms helps prevent health issues for students.				
3. I feel less stressed during school hours when I know the comfort rooms are clean.				
4. I believe that clean restrooms promote good mental well-being.				
5. I feel that using a clean restroom helps me avoid illness or infections.				
6. I feel at ease knowing that the hygiene standards in the comfort rooms meet my needs.				
7. I believe that maintaining hygiene in restrooms is essential for promoting student health.				
8. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better overall health for students.				
9. I feel safer using a clean restroom compared to an unclean one.				
10. I feel motivated to maintain better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean.				

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

192

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by the researchers of Senior High Grade 12 Student Center Academic Strand. We are requesting your cooperation to answer the questionnaire for the research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students". Your knowledge, experience, and response are a great help to us in achieving our goal. Rest assured that the data we will gather will remain absolutely confidential and will be used for academic purposes only. We are hoping that this request would meet your positive response. Again, thank you for accepting our concern. May God bless you.

I give my consent to participate to justify my submission for their research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School-Doña Josefa Campus". I am aware that the main purpose of this study is to find out how comfort room cleanliness affects the academic engagement of senior high school students. I also understand that my participation in this research is voluntary, and all experiences and answers from me will be treated confidentially and will only be used for this study. I understand that during the research study, at any time, I may withdraw from participation without any questions or loss of my privileges. Therefore, by answering, I am agreeing to participate in this research study.

THE IMPACT OF COMFORT ROOM CLEANLINESS TO THE ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Good Day! We are the researchers from CAS 12 strand, currently studying "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School-Doña Josefa Campus". This study aims to determine the impact of comfort room cleanliness on Academic Engagement of senior high school students. There are no significant risks associated with participating in this research. Your responses will be kept confidential and anonymous, and will only be used for this study. Thank you for your participation!

Name (optional): Eduardo, Jhon, D'Yan, F. Strand: Grade & Section Date: 03-04-2022

Direction: Read each statement and select the checkbox that best represents your level of agreement, with options ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

4 - Strongly Agree 3 - Agree 2 - Disagree 1 - Strongly Disagree

Section 1: Perceived Level of Cleanliness

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in DJC generally clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms on campus.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms in DJC meets acceptable hygiene standards.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7. I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Section 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		

192

5. I choose prefer to use a clean restroom, even if a dirty one is easier to access.

6. I feel embarrassed as a student when I see that the comfort rooms are well-maintained.

7. I believe that clean comfort rooms show the school's commitment to student well-being.

8. I feel that my overall satisfaction with school facilities depends on the cleanliness of the comfort rooms.

9. I believe that clean comfort rooms improve my overall school experience.

10. I think that dirty restrooms negatively impact my perception of the school.

Section 3: Impact on Student Focus and Concentration

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find it easier to focus in class when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2. I avoid using the comfort rooms when they are clean during school hours.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
3. I feel more focused on my studies after using a clean comfort room.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4. I feel more at ease during exams when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5. I feel more prepared to participate in class activities after using a clean restroom.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
6. I feel that clean comfort rooms help me concentrate better in lessons.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7. I feel more engaged in class discussions after using a well-maintained restroom.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
8. I believe that the cleanliness of the comfort rooms positively affects my attentiveness during lectures.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9. I find it easier to concentrate in school when I know the restrooms are well-maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
10. I believe that regular cleaning of the comfort rooms helps me stay focused on my studies.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Section 4: Impact on Student Health and Well-Being

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I believe that clean restrooms contribute positively to my physical health and well-being at school.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2. I feel confident that the cleanliness of the restrooms helps prevent health issues for students.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
3. I feel less stressed during school hours when I know the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4. I believe that clean restrooms promote good mental well-being.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5. I feel that using a clean restroom helps me avoid illness or infections.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
6. I feel at ease knowing that the hygiene standards in the comfort rooms meet my needs.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7. I believe that maintaining hygiene in restrooms is essential for promoting student health.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
8. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better overall health for students.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
10. I feel motivated to maintain better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

198

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by the researchers of course a senior grade 12 student. Scientific studies are an essential part of education in which our participation by our research is needed. The purpose of a research study is to determine the relationship between variables. The data that we collect will be used to describe the relationship and to be used by students preparing for the future. We are hoping that this research will help you become a better student. Agree to take part in this research and complete the questionnaire.

Section 1: Perceived Level of Cleanliness

Questions

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in DJC generally clean.				
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms all the time.				
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms in DJC meets acceptable hygiene standards.				
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.				
5. I believe there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.				
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.				
7. I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms.				
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.				
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.				
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.				

Section 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.				
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.				
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.				
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.				

198

Section 3: Impact on Student Focus and Concentration

Questions

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find it easier to focus in class when the comfort rooms are clean.				
2. I prefer using the comfort rooms when they are clean during school hours.				
3. I feel more focused on my studies after using a clean comfort room.				
4. I feel more at ease during class when the comfort rooms are clean.				
5. I feel more prepared to participate in class activities after using a clean restroom.				
6. I feel that clean comfort rooms help me concentrate better in lessons.				
7. I feel more engaged in class discussions after using a well-maintained restroom.				
8. I believe that the cleanliness of the comfort rooms positively affects my attentiveness during lectures.				
9. I find it easier to concentrate in school when I know the restrooms are well-maintained.				
10. I believe that regular cleaning of the comfort rooms helps me stay focused on my studies.				

Section 4: Impact on Student Health and Well-Being

Questions

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I believe that clean restrooms contribute positively to my physical health and well-being at school.				
2. I feel confident that the cleanliness of the restrooms helps prevent health issues for students.				
3. I feel less stressed during school hours when I know the comfort rooms are clean.				
4. I believe that clean restrooms promote good mental well-being.				
5. I feel that using a clean restroom helps me avoid illness or infections.				
6. I feel at ease knowing that the hygiene standards in the comfort rooms meet my needs.				
7. I believe that maintaining hygiene in restrooms is essential for promoting student health.				
8. I feel that a clean restroom environment supports better overall health for students.				
9. I feel safer using a clean restroom compared to an unclean one.				
10. I feel motivated to maintain better personal hygiene when the comfort rooms are clean.				

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

97

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by the researchers at Las Piñas City National Senior High School, Doña Josefa Campus. We are requesting your cooperation to assist our researchers for the research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students". Your knowledge, attitudes, and opinions are a very helpful in addressing our goal. We assure that the data we will gather will remain absolutely confidential and be used for scientific purposes only. We are hoping that this request would benefit your academic progress. Agree. Thank you for the insights and concern. Mrs. Carl Mae Jay

I give my voluntary consent to gather my information for this research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students" at Las Piñas City National Senior High School, Doña Josefa Campus. I do agree that the main purpose of this study is to find out how comfort room cleanliness affects the academic performance of senior high school students. I have understood that my participation in this research is voluntary and all information and answers that are will be treated confidentially and will only be used for this study. I understand that during the research study, in any time, I may withdraw from participation without any questions or loss of any privileges. Therefore, by participating, I am agreeing to participate in this research study.

THE IMPACT OF COMFORT ROOM CLEANLINESS TO THE ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Good Day! We are the researchers from SLS 13 Manila, currently studying "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School, Doña Josefa Campus". This study aims to improve the impact of comfort room cleanliness on Academic Engagement of senior high school students. There are no significant risks associated with participating in this research. Your responses will be kept confidential and anonymous, and will only be used for this study. Thank you for your participation!

Name (optional) _____ Sex: _____ Grade & Section: 121-12 PHENOLITE

Direction: Read each statement and select the checkbox that best represents your level of agreement, with options ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

4 - Strongly Agree 3 - Agree 2 - Disagree 1 - Strongly Disagree

Section 1: Perceived Level of Cleanliness

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in OJC generally clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms on campus.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms at OJC meets acceptable hygiene standards.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7. I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		

Section 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

98

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by the researchers at Las Piñas City National Senior High School, Doña Josefa Campus. We are requesting your cooperation to assist our researchers for the research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students". Your knowledge, attitudes, and opinions are a very helpful in addressing our goal. We assure that the data we will gather will remain absolutely confidential and be used for scientific purposes only. We are hoping that this request would benefit your academic progress. Agree. Thank you for the insights and concern. Mrs. Carl Mae Jay

I give my voluntary consent to gather my information for this research entitled "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students" at Las Piñas City National Senior High School, Doña Josefa Campus. I do agree that the main purpose of this study is to find out how comfort room cleanliness affects the academic performance of senior high school students. I have understood that my participation in this research is voluntary and all information and answers that are will be treated confidentially and will only be used for this study. I understand that during the research study, in any time, I may withdraw from participation without any questions or loss of any privileges. Therefore, by participating, I am agreeing to participate in this research study.

THE IMPACT OF COMFORT ROOM CLEANLINESS TO THE ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Good Day! We are the researchers from SLS 13 Manila, currently studying "The Impact of Comfort Room Cleanliness on the Academic Engagement of Senior High School Students at Las Piñas City National Senior High School, Doña Josefa Campus". This study aims to improve the impact of comfort room cleanliness on Academic Engagement of senior high school students. There are no significant risks associated with participating in this research. Your responses will be kept confidential and anonymous, and will only be used for this study. Thank you for your participation!

Name (optional) _____ Sex: _____ Grade & Section: _____

Direction: Read each statement and select the checkbox that best represents your level of agreement, with options ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

4 - Strongly Agree 3 - Agree 2 - Disagree 1 - Strongly Disagree

Section 1: Perceived Level of Cleanliness

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I find the comfort rooms in OJC generally clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2. I feel comfortable using the comfort rooms on campus.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I believe the cleanliness of the comfort rooms at OJC meets acceptable hygiene standards.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
4. I notice that the comfort rooms are regularly maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
5. I notice there is enough hygiene products (soap, toilet paper) in the comfort rooms.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
6. I rarely encounter unpleasant odors in the comfort rooms.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7. I observe minimal graffiti or vandalism in the comfort rooms.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
8. I believe that students contribute to keeping comfort rooms clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9. I rarely see trash left in the comfort rooms.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
10. I have noticed improvements in comfort room cleanliness over time.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		

Section 2: Impact on Student Satisfaction and Comfort

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I feel more satisfied with the school environment when the comfort rooms are clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2. I feel more relaxed when I know the comfort rooms are well-maintained.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
3. I feel more motivated to attend school when the comfort rooms are clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4. I feel more comfortable throughout the school day when the comfort rooms are clean.			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School
Doña Josefa Campus

CURRICULUM VITAE

General Academic Strand

Las Piñas City National Senior High School

Doña Josefa Campus

Relente, Randel P.	
Zone 3 Rebecca Compound Almanza Dos LasPiñas City	
09567806649	
randss@asia.com	

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

SECONDARY: SCHOOL	SCHOOL NAME	YEAR ATTENDED
SECONDARY: SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LAS PIÑAS CITY NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - DOÑA JOSEFA CAMPUS	2023 - 2025
SECONDARY: JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LASPIÑAS NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL ALMANZA/LYDIA AGUILAR NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL	2022 - 2023
PRIMARY: ELEMENTARY	PILAR VILLAGE ELEMENTARYSCHOOL	2013 - 2019

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age:	18
Birthday:	February 15, 2006
Height:	5'6
Religion:	Orthodox Christianity

SKILLS

Articulate Communication
Intellectual Curiosity

AWARD RECEIVED

NAME OF AWARD	GRADE LEVEL AWARD ATTENDED	YEAR ATTENDED
Top 1 (First Quarter) Best in Philippine Politics and Governance	12	2024

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Camila, Amiel Kirby G.	
Blk. 9 Lot 38 Dahlia St. T.S. Cruz Almanza Dos Las Piñas City	
09353563736	
amielkirbygraspelacamila@gmail.com	

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

LEVEL	SCHOOL	YEAR
SECONDARY: SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LAS PIÑAS CITY NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - DOÑA JOSEFA CAMPUS	2023 - 2025
SECONDARY: JUNIOR HIGHSCHOOL	LYDIA AGUILAR NATIONALHIGH SCHOOL	2022 - 2023
PRIMARY: ELEMENTARY	DON STEVEN FOUNDATION	2013 - 2019

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age:	17
Birthday:	August 13, 2007
Height:	5'7
Religion:	INC

SKILLS

Critical Thinking, Creativity

Adaptabilit , Innovative, Intellectual Curiosity

AWARD RECEIVED

NAME OF AWARD	GRADE LEVEL AWARD ATTENDED	YEAR ATTENDED
Top 5 (1st quarter) Top 8 (2nd quarter)	12	2024
Best in Introduction to World Religion	12	2024

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Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Quines, Shella Joy S.	
37 Cherry Blossom Equitable Village, Talon Quatro, Las Piñas City	
09679850580	
Shellasq27@gmail.com	

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

SECONDARY: SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LAS PIÑAS CITY NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - DOÑA JOSEFA CAMPUS	2023 - 2025
SECONDARY: JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL	MATUCAYNATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL	2019 - 2023
PRIMARY: ELEMENTARY	SINARAG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	2013 - 2019

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age:	17
Birthday:	July 14, 2007
Height:	4'9
Religion:	Catholic

SKILLS

Time Management

Multi-Tasking

AWARD RECEIVED

NAME OF AWARD	GRADE LEVEL AWARD ATTENDED	YEAR ATTENDED
Top 8 (First Quarter)	12	2024
Consistent With Honors	Grade 7-10	2019-2023

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Pisit, Yanli Jade S.	
Mahogany dulo zone 1 sitio pugad lawin Almanza dos Laspiñas City	
09815112358	
yanlijadepisit@gmail.com	

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

SECONDARY: SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LAS PIÑAS CITY NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - DOÑA JOSEFA CAMPUS	2023 - 2025
SECONDARY: JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LYDIA AGUILAR NATIONALHIGH SCHOOL	2022 - 2023
PRIMARY: ELEMENTARY	GOITO PIMENTEL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	2013 - 2019

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age:	18
Birthday:	February 19, 2007
Height:	5'8
Religion:	Catholic

SKILLS

Teamwork

Creativity, Communication

AWARD RECEIVED

NAME OF AWARD	GRADE LEVEL AWARD ATTENDED	YEAR ATTENDED
NONE	NONE	NONE

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Estuita, Sharen S.	
Saint Joseph Hope Street, Almanza Uno Laspiñas City	
08452476690	
Estuitasharen7@gmail.com	

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

SECONDARY: SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LAS PIÑAS CITY NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - DOÑA JOSEFA CAMPUS	2023 - 2025
SECONDARY: JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL	POLILLO ADVENTIST LEARNING INSTITUTE	2022 - 2023
PRIMARY: ELEMENTARY	BARANGAY BISLIAN, ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	2013 - 2019

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age:	18
Birthday:	December 18, 2006
Height:	5'7
Religion:	Catholic

SKILLS

Skills management		
Creativity		

AWARD RECEIVED

NAME OF AWARD	GRADE LEVEL AWARD ATTENDED	YEAR ATTENDED
Top4(3rd Quarter) Best in Oral Communication	11	2024

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Princess Anne T. Perez	
Zone 3 Kalye Pogi Sitio Pugad Lawin Almanza Dos Las Piñas City	
09926579870	
BAprincessperez0618@gmail.com	

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

SECONDARY: SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LAS PIÑAS CITY NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - DOÑA JOSEFA CAMPUS	2023 - 2025
SECONDARY: JUNIOR HIGHSCHOOL	LAS PIÑAS NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL - ALMANZA	2022 - 2023
PRIMARY: ELEMENTARY	PILAR VILLAGE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PILOTA	2013 - 2019

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age:	18
Birthday:	October 18, 2006
Height:	5'0
Religion:	Catholic

SKILLS

Time Management, Work Ethics

AWARD RECEIVED

NAME OF AWARD	GRADE LEVEL AWARD ATTENDED	YEAR ATTENDED
NCR Girls Champion	11	2023
NCR Girls Champion	12	2024
Division Meet Girls	12	2025

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Las Piñas City National Senior High School Doña Josefa Campus

Latorre, Jovan B.		
Ts cruz subdivision, blk 29 lot 19 Rosal St. Almanza dos las piñas city		
09625615982		
jovanlatorre391@gmail.com		
EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND		
SECONDARY: SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LAS PIÑAS CITY NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - DOÑA JOSEFA CAMPUS	2023 - 2025
SECONDARY: JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL	LYDIA AGUILAR NATIONALHIGH SCHOOL	2019 - 2023
PRIMARY: ELEMENTARY	ALMANZA ELEMENTARY TZ CRUZ ANNEX	2013 - 2019
PERSONAL INFORMATION		
Age:	19	
Birthday:	July 31, 2005	
Height:	5'7	
Religion:	Catholic	
SKILLS		
Self-Motivation		
Positivity, Patient		
AWARD RECEIVED		
NAME OF AWARD	GRADELEVELAWARD ATTENDED	YEAR ATTENDED
NONE	NONE	NONE

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TO GOD BE THE GLORY!

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